

Deliverable 1.1

Overview of Identification, Selection and Appraisal Practices for Long-Term Preservation of Data

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Deliverable Abstract

This report summarises existing identification, selection and appraisal practices for long-term digital data object preservation, across different domains, and identifies issues that potentially affect how preservation and the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of digital data objects may change over time.

The primary means of engaging with the wider digital preservation community on an inquiry into these practices - and the use of reference documents such as frameworks, guidelines and standards that guide preservation practice - was the delivery and analysis of a research survey. As such, this deliverable focuses mainly on the survey activity, the analysis of data received, and the implications of this research within and beyond EDEN WP1 activity.

DELIVERY SLIP

Contribution	Name	Partner	ORCID ID
Lead author(s)	Laura Molloy	CODATA	0000-0002-5214-4466
Contributor(s)	Micky Lindlar	TIB	0000-0003-3709-5608
Contributor(s)	Maria Benauer	TIB	0000-0003-1272-886X
Reviewer(s)	Helene N. Andreassen	UiT	0000-0001-9450-803X
Reviewer(s)	Karl Presser	PMT	0000-0001-7644-4116
Reviewer(s)	Anu Märkälä	CSC	0009-0009-1462-749X

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable data
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums
IGO	Intergovernmental Organisation
LTP	Long Term Preservation
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
Org class / org type	Organisation class / organisation type
RDM	Research Data Management
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
WP	Work Package

Definitions of other terms employed may be found in the RDM Terminology, adopted by EOSC EDEN as a key reference terminology and available at <https://vocabs.ardc.edu.au/viewById/685>.

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Executive summary

This report summarises existing identification, selection and appraisal practices for long-term digital data object preservation across different domains, and identifies issues that potentially affect how preservation and the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of digital data objects may change over time.

The primary means of engaging with the wider digital preservation community on an inquiry into these practices—and into the use of reference documents such as frameworks, guidelines and standards that guide preservation practice—was the delivery and analysis of a research survey. As such, this deliverable focuses mainly on the survey activity and the analysis of data received.

Our survey attracted 258 responses, of which 250 were valid, and engaged participants from the digital preservation sector: mostly practitioners, but also middle and senior managers from more than 17 organisation types across 31 countries.

We uncovered several key themes through this work: first, that the international digital preservation community works in a variety of settings and locations; second, that they are interested in sharing their experience and concerns; third, that the principles of FAIR data are familiar to our respondents but that the TRUST and CARE principles are less known or used; fourth, that a high proportion of respondents are working at an organisation where there is no agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ in the digital preservation context, rendering one of the premises upon which we are working in WP1 - “long-term preservation” - an unstable stable concept; and fifth, that resourcing, metadata quality, dealing with sensitive data, handling increasing data volume, and meeting changing user needs are all pressing issues for contemporary digital preservation practitioners.

These findings will be helpful to our ongoing work in EDEN WP1 as we identify findings useful to technical requirements in EDEN WP2, user journey maps and further investigations into discipline-specific needs in WP3, and dissemination and engagement of key stakeholders in WP4, as well as the Core Preservation Processes and the Reuse Fitness Framework activities within WP1.

The EDEN WP1 team is deeply grateful to every one of our digital preservation colleagues who took the time to participate in this survey.

1 Introduction and context

In this section, we provide a brief overview of the project and work package (WP), setting the task in context. We then briefly describe the task and how our desk research, consultation within the project and beyond, and the resulting survey, help us better understand contemporary identification, selection, appraisal and other relevant practices for ‘long-term’ preservation of data.

1.1 EOSC EDEN and WP1

The EOSC EDEN project seeks to enhance digital preservation strategies at European and national levels. At its core, the project will create a comprehensive framework to identify which data are candidates for digital preservation. This involves identifying quality metrics for the data on the levels of technical wrapping (i.e. format), description (i.e. metadata) and context (i.e. the content of the data). These metrics need to be aligned with the intended re-use scenario of the user community and be matched against the capability of the trustworthy digital archive responsible for preservation.

The framework will inform the initial identification process at the point of deposit and EOSC EDEN also aims to develop a model for re-appraisal of data throughout its lifecycle. Within the scope of the project, the model’s usability and practicality will be assessed through relevant communities, as early adopters, which will also help in developing tools and services to automate preservation processes. The model for re-appraisal will support the framework for digital preservation by ensuring that preservation efforts remain relevant over time.

WP1, ‘Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation’, has the main responsibility for development of the framework and model discussed above. This work is supported by activities to perform a landscape analysis of existing frameworks, guidelines and practices for identification, selection, and appraisal of data for long-term preservation; and to collect and transform user needs into requirements.

1.2 Task 1.1 and its research activities

To support progress toward WP1 objectives, Task 1.1 (T1.1) focuses on an overview and evaluation of existing frameworks, guidelines and practices that steer the identification, appraisal, and selection processes for data that are to be digitally preserved for a long-term period of time. This is achieved through analysis of desk research and surveys, working in collaboration with WP3 and WP4, and connecting with a wide network of discipline-specific communities in research, the cultural heritage domain and industry.

Investigation focuses on two main areas: i) what identification, selection and appraisal practices exist; ii) if and how these practices impact overall lifecycle management of the digital object within the archive. This activity will help us better understand if and how the FAIRness as well as technical and the content/information quality of the data are considered in overall lifecycle management. This approach also allows the task to understand the impact of moving targets such as cost, storage and service limitations that may impact appraisal and ingest decisions. The findings will be reported in D1.1 (this current report) and D1.2.

Task 1.1 will also receive the guidelines on tiered trustworthy digital preservation and the framework for information object re-use fitness from T1.2; and the model for re-appraisal from

T1.3, and will reposition each of these for maximum uptake by the stakeholder communities via the creation of checklists, guidelines, and sample policies.

A key initial activity of T1.1 is the early rollout of a survey to collect initial data from digital preservation professionals—within and beyond Europe—in order to better understand current practices including: the guidelines currently relied upon; current workflows; how digital objects are selected and appraised through quality checking; and contemporary understandings of ‘long-term’ in the context of digital preservation.

Please note that the text refers to tables the full list of which can be found in appendix B.

2 Designing the survey

Here we describe the way that we approached survey development as the first major activity of T1.1. This includes its basis in desk research and consultation within and outwith the EDEN project, our thought processes toward building survey questioning-routes and questions, and interactions with other parts of the project.

2.1 Writing the questions: aims and considerations

The survey was primarily put together by the WP1 Task Leads team, given the need to have input from the various tasks within the WP, and also due to the limited amount of effort in the WP for other partners. All WP participants were updated on progress and invited to contribute feedback.

The focus of the survey was to capture the contemporary knowledge and attitudes of those working in digital preservation in different organisational settings including discipline-specific communities, the cultural heritage domain, and industry (i.e. not just in organisations which are specifically funded as repositories). We wanted to understand specifically which guidelines and frameworks are in use when these professionals are working on identification, appraisal and selection of research data for long-term digital preservation. We also wanted to understand how these guidelines and frameworks inform practice in these areas.

We wanted to ensure that the survey would garner an enthusiastic response, to give us the best possible chance of reaching reliable findings. As well as attracting a high number of respondents, we were also clear that we wanted as many respondents as possible to complete and submit their response, rather than abandoning the survey before completion—a common issue in our survey-heavy sector. Accordingly, we made a point of writing the survey in language that was as direct and straightforward as possible, as we were aware that many respondents may not use English as a first language. Another of the challenges with language was to ensure that we did not unintentionally exclude those working in any particular organisation type (RPO, infrastructure, library, gallery, etc.) or size. We used terms and language appropriate to those working in digital preservation rather than, for example, other professions related to the research data sector. In doing this, we had a certain amount of confidence as members of the WP1 Task Leads team either work directly in digital preservation on a daily basis and have experience of different organisational settings, or have a substantial track record in policy, advocacy and capacity-building for digital preservation.

We were also keen to ensure that respondents could choose the level they are coming from within their organisation. As a result of desk research, we drew on the Library of Congress digital

preservation pyramid model of staff levels¹, which gave respondents the choice of identifying as a practitioner, middle manager, or senior manager/senior administrator (see figure 1). Again, this strategy brought considerations for language choice as we had to ensure the language we were using was appropriate for all three staff levels.

Figure 1: Staff levels in digital preservation. Image credit: Library of Congress Digital Preservation Outreach and Education programme.

Another factor in attracting and retaining participation was to ensure that the overall survey would not require a significant time investment for each respondent to complete. In the end, we edited the question instrument until timed tests of survey completion took about seven minutes (and potentially less than that, given certain question sequences when fewer follow-up questions are posed). There are two factors to this: a) the number of questions; and b) question design.

The number of questions was deliberately limited, and the scope was tightly focused. Question options were tailored to each respondent's choices. In the final product, we had twenty 'top-line' questions, i.e. the questions concerning digital preservation practice that are shown to every respondent, plus two further top-line administrative questions about future contact consent.

The twenty main top-line questions include questions designed by WP1 and also those introduced by our colleagues in WP3 ('Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use' - see more on this collaboration in report section 2.2).

We arranged the finalised question set thematically into four pages or sections on the survey tool, with a progress bar visible at all times to encourage the respondent to continue (see figure 2).

¹ <https://www.digitalpreservation.gov/education/educationneeds.html>

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Enhancing Digital Preservation Strategies at European and National Level

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

EOSC-EDEN survey on identification, appraisal and selection of digital data for long-term digital preservation.

Disclaimer
The European Commission is not responsible for the content of questionnaires created using the EUSurvey service - it remains the sole responsibility of the form creator and manager. The use of EUSurvey service does not imply a recommendation or endorsement, by the European Commission, of the views expressed within them.

Pages Start [Section] [Section] [Section] [Section] [Section]

1. About your organisation and role

Your organisation type is:

- Academic journal publisher
- Commercial digital preservation service
- Discipline-agnostic data repository
- Discipline-specific data repository
- Museum or gallery
- National archive
- National library
- Non-commercial digital preservation service
- Non-governmental or intergovernmental organisation
- Research infrastructure
- Research performing organisation
- University library

Views
Standard [Accessibility Mode](#)

Languages
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Figure 2: First page of survey questions, showing the progress bar at top.

In total, the survey displayed six pages of material: a welcome page, including the consent agreement; four pages of questioning about digital preservation guidance and practices; and a ‘thank you’ page to conclude, with an option for the respondent to supply their contact information, and to indicate their interest in further contact.

2.2 Collaboration with other work packages within EDEN

Questions were crafted primarily by WP1, but also solicited directly from WP3, ‘Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use’, who needed to gather some appropriate insights from discipline-specific points of view. The two WPs worked together to ensure that the questions were within scope, that the language was consistent with the rest of the survey, that questions were structured appropriately for the tool, and that the questions were of a sufficiently concise nature and number in order to keep the overall survey within the 5 to 7 minute response time for which we were aiming.

WP1 supported WP3 with survey-related activities in addition to the insertion of questions. For example, we prepared and published a copy of the full questions set online² to allow reference by a concurrent WP3 deliverable³, and made the survey data (both the full data set and the WP3-specific subset) available to WP3 through the project's secure data environment (SD Connect)⁴. Our consent form allows us to share the data received from respondents across the EDEN project and also with our sister project FIDELIS. There is no plan to publish the full data set due to the level of identifying remarks. Accordingly, we have removed identifying detail from the qualitative data presented in this public report, alongside a fulsome numerical account of aggregated results (see report section 5).

EDEN WP4, 'Expert and Community Engagement', was also a valued collaborator. We communicated the survey activity timeline with WP4 at an early stage, and also shared the draft questions with WP4 and received their feedback. WP4 was also active in the promotion and distribution of the survey once it opened. We also received guidance from WP4 and WP5, 'Coordination, Sustainability and Strategic Alignment', on the wording of the informed consent agreement (see Appendix D) and arrangements for data storage.

In terms of collaboration beyond the EDEN project, we were in touch throughout the process with the FIDELIS team who were running a survey earlier in the year, but with a clearly different focus. However, the FIDELIS data was not made available until after the EDEN T1.1 survey was created and online.

2.3 Survey questions

The final set of survey questions is presented and discussed here. This overview addresses only the 'top-line' questions: that is to say, the set of questions that are asked to every respondent. Subsequent questioning routes differed, depending upon the response given to each of the top-line questions; i.e. depending upon the answer chosen for a given top-line question, a subsequent set of relevant subsidiary questions was presented in order to procure the fullest possible information from each respondent.

This approach gives the participant a more tailored set of questions to answer, and minimises time spent by the respondent on questions that are not relevant to them. This helps keep the participant engaged and so encourages participation through to the end of the survey. What we learned from each section, including the subsidiary questions, will be discussed in more detail in section 5, below.

The topics addressed by the survey questions, and the thinking behind each of the 4 survey sections, are discussed section-by-section here, in order to provide a clear overview of the structure of the final survey design and the scope of questioning.

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528660>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789261>. D3.1 contains a more detailed presentation of the discipline-specific questions.

⁴ Permitted under the conditions of the informed consent statement (Appendix D).

2.3.1 Survey section 1 questions: “About your organisation and role”

The questions in survey section 1 allow us to gather the basic contextual information for each case or record (i.e. the full set of responses from a given respondent).

Section	Question no.	Topic
1		About your organisation and role.
	1.1	Organisation type.
	1.2	Country or state in which organisation is based/headquartered.
	1.3	Organisation size.
	1.4	Respondent’s own role within the organisation.
	1.5*	The specific research discipline(s), if any, for which the organisation preserves digital objects.

**=question proposed by WP3.*

Q1.1 allows us to get a sense of the various types of organisation in which digital preservation is happening. This ‘organisation type’ question asked respondents to pick from a list, with the ability to choose as many organisation types as relevant. This picklist was developed during a dedicated breakout session in the project kick-off meeting early in 2025. Organisation types were also suggested by participants from various work packages in the project.

Q1.2 allows us to get a sense of geographic spread—at least of the main locations of organisations, if not necessarily where individuals are actually based personally. The picklist for this question was supplied by the EU Survey tool and uses the UN state list⁵. We added an “Other” option for those states/countries who are not recognised by the UN list. One option only could be chosen from the list.

Q1.3 uses the EU classification of organisation size which gives four different sizes, from which to choose one option. This enriches our understanding of the organisations who have responded, and an additional vector along which to analyse the resulting data.

Q1.4 draws upon the Library of Congress pyramid of three staff levels, as previously discussed. We specified in our communications that we welcomed multiple responses from any given organisation, should that be thought appropriate by respondents. This question was a way of differentiating between these multiple submissions, should they occur. It is worth noting, however, that we do not have a systematic way of connecting multiple submissions from the same team or department, nor have we attempted to do so.

⁵ <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/member-states>, as it stood on 2 May 2025.

Q1.5 is the first of the questions from WP3 and deploys the two-tier UNESCO Fields Of Research and Development (FORD) standard taxonomy⁶ for describing research areas. This question allows us again to analyse the resulting data along discipline-specific vectors. We included options for "Generic/no discipline speciality" as well as "Multidisciplinary" with an option to specify the specific mixture of disciplines.

The structure of these questions in survey section 1 demonstrates how we have—whenever possible—deployed appropriate and well-established standards and ontologies (e.g. of states, research fields) in order to make our work as interoperable and comparable as possible with other research that uses those standards.

2.3.2 Survey section 2 questions: “About frameworks and guidelines for identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation”

In survey section 2, we wanted a simple way to get a sense of the reference materials, standards, guidelines and other frameworks that are currently used by digital preservation practitioners in their day-to-day work.

Section	Question no.	Topic
2		About frameworks and guidelines for identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation.
	2.1	A list of well-known frameworks and standards in this area; respondents are asked to choose for each one whether they had heard of and currently use/heard of but do not currently use/have not heard of.
	2.2	Existence of agreed or working definition of "long-term" in the context of digital preservation.

In Q2.1, we presented a list of fifteen well-known frameworks and standards that we gathered from our desk research and from the digital preservation experts in the WP, and presented for consideration and review to WP1 and WP4. We also made sure that we allowed a free text option for survey respondents to contribute a description of any other such documents that they wished to add to the list of options.

Two of the documents that we added as answer options, in consultation with WP3, include: a) the respondent’s own institutional preservation policy; and b) their organisational collection development policy/statement/strategy. When either of these were selected, subsidiary questions asked for the relevant URL if available.

Q2.2 asked whether the organisation had an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ in the context of digital preservation, and provided a simple yes/no answer option. When “yes” was selected, the respondent received a text box to enter this definition. A further text box gives space

⁶ OECD (2015), *Frascati Manual 2015: Guidelines for Collecting and Reporting Data on Research and Experimental Development*, The Measurement of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Activities, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264239012-en>, p. 59.

for information about where the definition comes from; for example, "Our organisation wrote a definition", or "From standard x". Where the respondent answered "no", we asked a further question on why there is not an existing definition in place, offering four likely answering options (including a free text box for more detail). The aim here was to support the respondent to feel able to answer why not, and give us more information on the influences on that decision, rather than making the respondent feel defensive about the lack of a definition at their organisation. This allows us to understand, inter alia, whether those without a definition think that this is an important issue, or something that does not apply to them; and whether or not a definition may be currently in development at their organisation.

2.3.3 Survey section 3 questions: "About current practices in identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation"

In survey section 3, we were interested in finding out more about current practices.

Section	Question no.	Topic
3		About current practices in identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation.
	3.1	How digital data objects for preservation usually enter the organisation.
	3.2	Assessment of quality of digital data objects at point of ingest.
	3.3	Regular reassessment of the quality of preserved digital data objects.
	3.4	Initial preservation period for digital data objects that have been selected for "long term" digital preservation.
	3.5	What happens to objects after the initial preservation period.
	3.6	Any further remarks on current practices in identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation.

Q3.1 examines the collection/acquisition route, prior to formal ingest processes.

Q3.2 then drills into whether assessment of quality is done at this point. If yes, then we offer a detailed and fairly complex list of types of quality check or assessment at ingest to choose from, so we have a better idea of exactly what happens at ingest. These types of quality check map against the three different levels of quality we mentioned in report section 1: technical wrapping (i.e. format), description (i.e. metadata) and context (i.e. the content of the data). Considerable detail was added to this section as this delivers most of the knowledge we gather specifically about identification, selection and appraisal practices.

In Q3.3, respondents can indicate whether they regularly reassess the quality of digital data objects that have been selected for preservation, during the preservation period. If they answer "yes", there is an opportunity to discuss the frequency with which this reassessment occurs.

We then returned to the idea of what ‘long-term’ digital preservation means for different organisations. Q3.4 asks this, and in doing so validates the earlier responses to how organisations define ‘long-term’.

In Q3.5, we want to know what happens next, once the initial defined (or undefined!) preservation period has expired, and we offer several likely options for what might happen plus an open text option for any other choices to be explained.

The section finishes with a text field for any other comments about current practices (Q3.6).

2.3.4 Survey section 4 questions: “Discipline-specific requirements for long-term preservation of digital objects”

In this final section of substantive questions, the majority of the material is composed of the discipline-specific questions initiated by WP3⁷.

Section	Question no.	Topic
4		Discipline-specific requirements for long-term preservation of digital objects.
	4.1*	Descriptive metadata standards commonly used in the organisation.
	4.2*	Whether the organisation recommends (a list of) preferred file formats.
	4.3*	Whether the organisation accepts sensitive data/data that requires specific protection.
	4.4*	Whether the designated community has needs that the organisation does not currently address.
	4.5*	Factors that could reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of digital data objects preserved by the organisation.
	4.6	Any other comments.

*=question proposed by WP3.

Q4.1 supplies the respondent with a list of descriptive metadata standards, from which they can choose those in use at their organisation.

In Q4.2, we ask whether file formats are recommended. If the answer is “yes”, we ask for the URL to the list, if available. If the answer is “no”, we ask for the most common formats stored in the repository. We specifically avoided asking for all formats that are stored as this would potentially be onerous for the respondent and wouldn’t tell us enough about the *predominant* formats preserved by the organisation.

⁷ See D3.1 for elaboration: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789261>

Q4.3 digs into the issue of sensitive data or data that requires specific protections. For this list of options, we used the list provided in the UNESCO Recommendation On Open Science⁸. For each category of sensitive/protected data identified as relevant, the respondent is invited to specify the types of protection measure(s) taken by their organisation.

Q4.4 changes the pace of questioning by offering a very open idea with no easy answers—whether the organisation’s designated community has unmet needs. Initially the respondent is invited to choose “yes”, “no” or “I don’t know”. If “yes”, they are given an open text field in which to describe any unmet designated community needs of which the respondent is aware.

Q4.5 was an opportunity to ensure that we specifically address FAIR data, an important concern of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Like the preceding question, this one gives the respondent an opportunity to reflect on progress so far and likely considerations for the future. As supporting information, we provide a link to an overview of the FAIR principles. Again, respondents have a free text box to record their thoughts.

Finally Q4.6 is simply an opportunity to make any other comments that the respondent has not felt prompted to do elsewhere. This was the final digital preservation-specific top-line question.

2.3.5 Survey section 5: “Thank you”

The final page of the survey was used to thank the respondent, to ask for the respondent’s email address if they wished to share it, to provide an opportunity to volunteer for further contact with no obligation, and to give a link to the project webpage.

In the next section of this report, we will move from discussion of the intellectual to the practical preparations made for the survey.

3 The survey in action

In this report section, we provide a brief account of getting the survey online; any questions, enquiries or issues that were raised during the live survey period; the choice of tool and any problems or advantages brought by the tool; how and to whom we promoted the survey; how many responses we received; and any limits or biases we identified.

3.1 Getting the survey online: when and how

Our first practical decision was to set a timeframe for the surveying activity, with respect to the requirements of the current deliverable as well as other dependencies within WP1 and other EDEN work packages. Once we had this timetable agreed within the work package, we communicated it to other relevant parts of the project so that they had a reasonable expectation of when we would need to focus on promotion, and when they were likely to have access to the resulting data set. We opened the survey on Friday 2 May 2025 (1 May was a public holiday) and closed it on Tuesday 1 July 2025.

Our second decision was to find a suitable online tool for hosting the survey. This needed to be well-resourced and stable, EU-based, and with an acceptable approach to data security. It also needed to have proven functionality for downloading and exporting data, and ideally offer some

⁸ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about?hub=686>; and <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>

functionality for analysis of the results. All these requirements were met by the EU Survey tool⁹ and testing confirmed that input and branding were relatively straightforward, the tool had the functionality we needed for question design and question flow, and the results would be straightforward to export from the tool. Given that the EDEN project is EU-funded, this felt like a good fit for that reason too.

3.2 Recruiting respondents

Recruitment of respondents to the survey (also referred to as 'survey participants' in this report) began with survey publication on 2 May 2025 and continued throughout the period of time that the survey was open for response. EDEN WP1, WP3 and WP4 worked closely together on the promotion of the survey to various networks and different parts of the global digital preservation community. WP3 was again a valued partner particularly in communicating with potential discipline-specific respondents.

In order to minimise duplication of effort, the Task 1.1 lead set up a project-only shared worksheet to track the survey promotional activity (see figure 3). In this sheet, the team logged the organisation, list or group that might be worth contacting for responses; the date of initial contact; the EDEN colleague responsible; any named individual recipient applicable; the stakeholder type; the date any follow-up contact was made; and any relevant further notes. This sheet became one of our main collaboration tools as we moved through the promotional activity.

WP1 also drafted and shared short texts suitable for different promotional contexts, including one each for social media; text-only mailing lists; blogs and newsletters; and a template upon which personal emails could be based.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
	Organisation/List	Date initial contact	By whom (EDEN)	Named individual recipient (where applicable)	Stakeholder type	Date followup contact/s	Notes
3	CODATA Intl list	2025-05-14	Laura	-	Mailing list for multiple types		sent to A
4	digipres jislist	2025-05-15	Laura	-	Mailing list for multiple types		
5	RESEARCH-DATAMAN@JISMAIL.AC.UK	2025-05-20	Helena Watson OPF	-	Mailing list for multiple types		
6	OPF members	2025-05-15	Micky	-	Community based organisation Research infrastructure	Reminder sent by J	
7	CODATA National Committees	2025-05-14	Laura	-	Open science and fair initiative		sent to A https://c
8	WorldFAIR list	2025-05-14	Laura	-	Mailing list for multiple types Open science and fair initiative Research performing organisation Discipline-specific community		sent to A
9	nestor	2025-06-02	Micky	-	Mailing list for multiple types Community based organisation		
10	nestor sub-AG Appraisal RDM?	2025-06-02	Maria	-	Community based initiative		
11	NFDI AG LTA	2025-06-02	Micky	-	Research infrastructure		
12	forschungsdaten-dfn-list	2025-05-15	Micky	-	Mailing list for multiple types Research performing organisation Research infrastructure		
13	NatLA-list	2025-05-15	Micky	-	Library Policy maker Repository University		
14	Rosetta-User-Group	2025-06-02	Micky	-	Library Archive		
15					Open science and fair initiative		MB: I car

Figure 3: Collaborative worksheet for tracking promotional activity.

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/auth/login>

We proceeded more cautiously with efforts to translate the announcements, because the survey was available only in English and we did not want to build a false impression to speakers of other languages that the survey would also be translated. However, we translated the announcement text into French, German, Spanish, Dutch, and Chinese (see Appendix E), in which we noted that the survey itself was in English. Our ability to create competent translations of the promotional text was thanks to the presence of fluent speakers of these languages in the project team and also in our wider networks.

3.3 Responses received

We received 258 responses by the survey closing date. After removing spam and blank responses, we were left with 250 valid responses.

4 Analysing the survey

We analysed 250 survey responses using a mixture of simple quantitative and qualitative methods.

Quantitative methods offered an effective way to investigate patterns, correlations and causalities among responses to closed (yes/no) questions (e.g. by testing contextual information as collected in survey section 1 against answers in other sections). Qualitative methods gave us ways to work with the textual data collected by the open questions and helped us to identify emerging themes generated by our respondents.

4.1 Methods

The choice of the EU Survey tool was partly influenced by its useful analytical tooling. It provides a spreadsheet output and also visualisations of responses to some of the questions. This was our starting point for an analysis that would be fit for purpose, i.e. prioritising clarity of output of this first analysis, whilst remaining as simple as possible methodologically. However, as we allowed multiple responses for most of the questions, the analysis of complex answers (i.e. multiple answers from a respondent to the same question) exceeded the functionalities of the survey tool (see report Section 4.2 'Limits and bias'). Moreover, the tool reported the results of multi-option questions in relation to the total number of respondents. This approach provided only a high-level perspective and occasionally produced counterintuitive results (e.g. tables in which relative values exceeded 100%).

Further statistical analysis and visual data interpretation was therefore performed using Excel (version 2016) to filter and visualise data in a more flexible way. The functionalities of Excel were used to apply additional categories to the responses and sort information to prepare the data for representation by various kinds of visualisation. In the next step, diagrams (as used throughout this deliverable) were created to identify proportions, relationships and other patterns typically highlighted through visual data representation. In addition to Excel, Datawrapper¹⁰ was used to visualise the geographical spread of the survey.

We are aware that our current audience is keen for straightforward messaging as a result of the survey work. By providing both a visual and textual interpretation of the survey respondents, we aim to provide multiple entry points to our findings, and ensure that the results can be interpreted

¹⁰ <https://www.datawrapper.de/>

easily. We have tried to deliver that here and in the various presentations the WP1 team has made on this activity.

We have used open tools whenever possible for analysis and visualisation, including Taguette¹¹, OpenRefine¹² and Datawrapper.

4.2 Limits and bias

One of the decisions we made early in the promotional process was to pursue a global response. We have only been partly successful in that, despite targeted communications to the global South. Of the 250 valid responses netted by the survey, we have none from the African continent and very few from Central and South America (2 responses, both from the same country), and Asia (9 responses in total, from across 4 countries). This means that we cannot claim any particular insight into digital preservation behaviour in those large parts of the globe. This was something of a disappointment to the team and an outcome we are keen to learn from.

Another bias of the data is that we received a disproportionate response from participants based in Germany (66 responses). We are very grateful to our digital preservation colleagues in Germany for their enthusiasm, and highly value their responses, but the fact remains that the high proportion of responses from Germany (26.4% of all 250 valid responses) provides an overemphasis of the views from this location (see section 5.1.2 for more on the geographical spread of responses).

Moreover, the generalisability of overall findings is limited by the fact that, as will be seen in section 5.1.1, the survey received varying levels of response from different organisation classes (“org classes”)¹³, leading to a distortion of the results in favour of the org class “Archive” (26.8% of all 250 valid responses, including all archive-related organisation types).

Another complicating factor for straightforward survey analysis is that respondents were permitted to select multiple answers and an additional “Other” option was provided when none of the responses applied. We deliberately employed this approach to capture the full diversity of the digital preservation community in terms of organisations, practices and knowledge systems. However, it also results in a complex dataset and leads to the effect that direct causal relationships cannot always be clearly established (particularly in the case of multiple responses) by means of quantitative methods. Addressing multiple response questions would require further time-intensive qualitative research. Consequently, our methodology employed in this deliverable favours a top-down exploration of the field rather than detailed causal attribution.

¹¹ <https://app.taguette.org/>

¹² <https://openrefine.org/>

¹³ An org class is a grouping of the different types of organisation (‘org type’) in order to simplify analysis. For example, org types “National library” and “University library” are combined for analysis - where appropriate - into org class “Library”. See report section 5.1.1 for more detail.

5 Results and findings

In this chapter, we set out the results derived from the survey activity, organised by survey section; and the findings that emerge from these results - that is to say, what these results indicate in the context of the contemporary digital preservation sector.

5.1 Survey section 1: Profile of participants

Questions in survey section 1 aim to gather information on the overall profile of respondents: namely, organisation size, type and location, and the position of the respondent within the organisation.

5.1.1 Organisation type and organisation class

All 250 valid responses provided at least one definition of the respondent's organisation type (coded "org type" for short).

As can be seen in Table 1, university libraries (n=61) were the most common organisational type for respondents. The second most popular category in the first round of coding was "Unlisted: another type of organisation" (n=44). The popularity of this category indicates that we made a design error in writing this question because it shows that many respondents did not find their organisation type amongst the options offered. Accordingly, in a further round of analysis, we sorted the responses from the "Unlisted" category into those categories to which they were relevant, where those existed, and generated new categories as required. In Table 1, the newly-generated categories are shown, and clearly identified with the prefix "Other".

It turned out in analysis that the "Unlisted" category was so popular because we had not offered 'university archive' or 'local government archive' as options. As can be seen in the table of results below, the newly-generated categories, "Other: Municipal / local / county / state govt archive", and "Other: University archive/scientific org archive" were both popular, attracting 10 and 14 responses respectively.

Four responses - "Governmental organisation", "Library sistem" (sic), "Local authority", and "Religious Congregation" - remain unassigned to a new or existing category, because there is not enough information supplied throughout the rest of the record in each case to confidently assign the org type response to the correct category. This last group of four were thus put together in Table 1 as a category labelled "Unassigned".

Table 1: Organisation type categories (initial analysis).

Organisation type ('Org type')	n	Ratio (of 250)
University library ¹⁴	61	24.4%
RPO (inc. Other: University) ¹⁵	40	16.0%
National archive	37	14.8%
Research infrastructure	35	14.0%
Discipline-specific data repository	26	10.4%
Discipline-agnostic data repository	19	7.6%
Museum or gallery	17	6.8%
Other: Municipal / local / county / state government archive	14	5.6%
National library	12	4.8%
Non-commercial digipres service	11	4.4%
Other: University archive/scientific organisation archive	10	4.0%
NGO / IGO ¹⁶	8	3.2%
Academic publisher	6	2.4%
Other: Company archive	5	2.0%
Other: Private archive ¹⁷	4	1.6%
Unassigned	4	1.6%
Commercial digipres service ¹⁸	3	1.2%
Other: Governmental or state library	3	1.2%

In the survey design, we intentionally allowed multiple answers for organisation type to capture the diversity of how digital preservation can be accommodated in institutional terms. Although revealing insightful information about the complexity of organisational and disciplinary settings in which digital preservation takes place, the finding that 18% of all respondents indicated working in an organisation with more than one function complicated the analysis of the survey by impeding meaningful comparison.

To accommodate this complexity, we introduced the notion of 'multifunctional' organisations. This allows us to disambiguate between those organisations that are described as having one function only, and those where the respondent has selected more than one function to describe their organisation (see Figure 4).

¹⁴ "University library" category includes those responses that used this term (60) plus 1 further response identified via "Unlisted other".

¹⁵ RPO category includes those responses that used this term (38) plus 2 further responses identified via "Unlisted other".

¹⁶ Includes 7 responses that chose "NGO or IGO" plus one "Unlisted other", assigned to this category.

¹⁷ The org type category "Other: Private archive" is unusual in that it is not used in conjunction with other categories by respondents, i.e. each of the four responses in this category only chose this category and no other organisation type in conjunction with it.

¹⁸ The org type category "Commercial digital preservation service" is unusual in that it is not used in conjunction with other categories by respondents, i.e. each of the three responses in this category only chose this category and no other organisation type in conjunction with it.

Figure 4: Extent of multifunctionality among organisations.

We can see from Figure 4 that the vast majority of respondents described their organisation as having a single function. The group of “Multifunctional” organisations, as developed during subsequent analysis (see Figure 6), emerged as the second most popular category (Figure 5). To clearly differentiate between organisational types as indicated by the respondents and the “multifunctional” type as developed during analysis, the latter is highlighted in a different colour pattern.

Distribution of respondents by organisation type

Figure 5: Distribution of respondents by organisation type, including the ‘multifunctional’ category.

To enable the triangulation of “org type” with other questions, we identified the need to normalise and simplify the organisation type ontology. By grouping org types into broader categories, which we called organisation classes (see Figure 6), we were able to maintain a manageable number of variables for the comparative analysis and visualisation. The benefit of doing so was to explore differing trends among sectoral boundaries.

Organisation class	Organisation type
Academic publisher	Academic publisher
Archive	National archive
	Other: Municipal / local / county / state government archive
	University archive/scientific organisation archive
	Other: Private archive
	Other: Company archive

Library	National library
	University library
	Other: Governmental or state library
Multifunctional	All responses indicating more than one function from the list of organisation types
Repository	Discipline-specific data repository
	Discipline-agnostic data repository
Research performing organisation	RPO
	Other: University
Museum or gallery	Museum or gallery
Research infrastructure	Research infrastructure
Digital preservation service	Non-commercial digital preservation service
	Commercial digital preservation service
Unassigned/other	NGO / IGO
	Unassigned

Figure 6: Organisation types grouped into classes.

The organisation types were sorted into broader classes based on their naming. For example, the class ‘Archive’ comprises all org types which a) have a single function; and b) explicitly reference “archive”. We assume that such a classification continues to reflect the professional context, institutional identity, and knowledge systems within these organisations, and allows us to make generalisations based on sector.

As can be seen in the table below (see Figure 7), the survey was most successful in reaching the “Archive” org class, followed by libraries and multifunctional organisations while repositories, museums or galleries, and research infrastructures make up a significantly smaller proportion.

Figure 7: Distribution of respondents by organisation class.

Whereas the initial classification (see Table 1) comprised 18 org types, the “org class” classification, as applied in the following diagrams, include 9 org classes. It is important to note that the organisation type, ‘Academic journal publisher’ is excluded from subsequent analyses due to its small size, with only one response being received in this category¹⁹.

5.1.2 Geographical location

We asked, “In which country is your organisation based?” The EU Survey tool offers two different potential schema for answers—one was the list of EU member countries and the other, a list of United Nations member states²⁰. We opted for the latter, adding the caveat of an “Other” option for states that were not represented therein.

In general, this question had a high response rate, with every respondent except one providing an answer. The answers received to this question are listed from most to least frequent in Table 2 ([Appendix B](#)), and illustrated in Figures 8 and 9 below.

One respondent, from a discipline-specific data repository, chose the “Other” option, and provided the following information in the explanatory text field: “Int. federation of discipline data repositories”, but did not indicate where this federation was headquartered.

The main trend is that the majority of responses (n=183) are from Europe including the UK (see Figure 8), and North America comprising USA and Canada (n=40). We received 14 responses

¹⁹ i.e. one response of this organisation type alone. The other five respondents that included “academic journal publisher” in their org type response also chose other functions to describe their organisation and as such were included in the category “multifunctional” in Figure 7 and subsequent analysis.

²⁰ As these lists stood at 30 April 2025.

from Australasia, 9 responses from Asia, 2 from central and south Americas and none from Africa (see figure 9).

Figure 8: European distribution of respondents.

Figure 9: Global distribution of respondents.

5.1.3 Organisation size

In order to explore organisation size, we supplied a set of four categories of organisation size as used by the European Union²¹, from which the respondent could choose. Responses here were again healthy with only two respondents failing to answer.

As can be seen in Figure 10 below and Table 3 ([Appendix B](#)), the largest single group of respondents (37.6%) chose Large, i.e. their organisational setting has 251 or more full-time equivalent (FTE) employees. This was followed by Medium (30.4%) which represents organisations with between 51 and 250 FTE. We were, however, also pleased to receive so many responses from small (11 to 50 FTE) and micro (less than 10 FTE) organisations: together, small and micro organisations provided 31.2% of all responses.

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Enterprise_size

Figure 10: Distribution of organisation size.

We also analysed the organisation size categories by organisation class ('organisation class' being the groupings of organisation type that we developed during analysis, as introduced in section 5.1.1 above): see Figure 11.

Figure 11: Distribution of organisation size by organisation class.

This distribution of organisation size by organisation class indicates that the “Archive” and “Digital preservation service” classes have the most even distribution of organisation types in comparison

with, say, the “Library” class which predictably skews towards larger organisation sizes, or the “Repository” class which skews towards smaller sizes.

It should be noted that, due to the limitations of the design of this question, we are unable to draw broad conclusions about whether and how practice differs between large organisations and smaller ones. As was pointed out by respondents several times in the comments, a large organisation may still have a very small digital preservation team and/or budget. If what we needed to understand was the level of resource available, we would have needed to have asked a question directly about an annual budget, including for staffing; we suspected that in many cases, colleagues would not be able or willing to respond directly to such a question. This question on organisation size, then, was a proxy to understand the different contexts in which digital preservation teams exist but cannot be presumed to carry more analytical weight than that. We are interested in further exploration of these different working contexts.

5.1.4 Participant role within organisation

Participants were encouraged to identify the level of their role within the organisation, choosing from the Library of Congress pyramid of staff levels, as previously discussed in Section 2.1. All respondents except one provided a response to this question (see Figure 12, below, and Table 4, [Appendix B](#)). The majority (66%) identified wholly or partly as practitioners: that is to say, individuals who spend the majority of their workday actively engaged in digital preservation activity. On this basis, we are pleased to have directly reached so many digital preservation colleagues to better understand their practice.

We permitted participants to select more than one role if necessary; this option was intended to accommodate those particularly working on small teams or in small organisations, who regularly fulfill more than one role within the team/organisation. We found that 22 respondents (8.8% of all participants) chose this option and the further analysis of those multiple roles is shown in Figure 12 below. As can be seen in the column on the right of this figure, the majority of those respondents who hold multiple roles combine the roles of ‘Practitioner’ and ‘Middle management’.

Figure 12: Organisational role type: overall breakdown (left); and breakdown of those responses (n=22) with more than one role (right).

5.1.5 Discipline focus (if any)

Survey questions around the discipline specificity of preserved data objects were contributed by WP3, as discussed above, and the data gathered in response to discipline-specific questions was shared with WP3 at an early stage after the survey closure.

Our desk research identified the Fields Of Research and Development (FORD) taxonomy of discipline areas²² as the most appropriate taxonomy for our use, due to its discipline- and funder-agnostic design, and its wide international adoption by - amongst others - the OECD Frascati manual²³, the United Nations system including the UNESCO Institute for Statistics²⁴, the International Science Council, etc.

Respondents were asked to choose the research discipline(s) relevant to the digital objects held by their organisation. We provided the classification options from the FORD taxonomy, plus an additional option each for "Generic/no discipline speciality" and "We have a specific interdisciplinary scope".

Respondents were able to choose more than one of these discipline areas in their response, and to subsequently select subdisciplines as appropriate, in order to provide useful data for WP3 purposes. However, the top-level classification of disciplines was sufficient for our purposes in WP1. Responses are reported in Table 5 and Figure 13.

Table 5: Discipline-specific relevance of preserved digital data objects.

Digital objects of which research discipline(s) are stored by your organisation? Please select as many as apply.	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 250)
Generic / no discipline speciality	138	55.2%
Humanities and the arts	109	43.6%
Social sciences	99	39.6%
Natural sciences	83	33.2%
Engineering and technology	64	25.6%
Medical and health sciences	62	24.8%
Agricultural and veterinary sciences	32	12.8%
We have a specific interdisciplinary scope.	16	6.4%
No Answer	0	0.00%

²² <https://uis.unesco.org/node/3079686>; <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/classifications/Family/Detail/1039>

²³ https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/frascati-manual-2015_9789264239012-en.html, p. 59.

²⁴ <https://www.uis.unesco.org/en>

All respondents provided at least one answer, with ‘Generic/no discipline speciality’ being the most frequent response. ‘Humanities and the arts’ was the second most popular response (43.6%), followed by ‘Social sciences’, ‘Natural sciences’, ‘Engineering and technology’, ‘Medical and health sciences’, and finally ‘Agricultural and veterinary sciences’.

Those who indicated a specific interdisciplinary scope (n=16, 6.4%) were subsequently asked to identify what this was in a text field²⁵.

Figure 13: Discipline specificity, each as percentage of all responses.

We noticed that some responses appeared contradictory as respondents indicated ‘generic’ while also ticking one or multiple disciplines; or indicated ‘generic’ while ticking all disciplines provided, leading to a large proportion of indications of multiple disciplines. We therefore created a new analytical category for responses to this question, “Multiple disciplines”. This allowed us to sort the reported discipline specificity of organisations by either their single research area, where this was indicated, or by this new category, “Multiple disciplines” (see Figure 14).

²⁵ In at least 2 of these textual descriptions, what emerges is not a specific interdisciplinary field or research area per se, but rather a list of various subdiscipline areas that exist elsewhere in the taxonomy. These cases would have been more accurately handled by choice of those subdisciplines from the taxonomy, all of which could be made visible to the respondent. But we recognise the convenience of quick text entry!

Figure 14: Organisations sorted by discipline specificity, including new category 'Multiple disciplines'.

5.1.6 Survey section 1: reflections

This initial section of the survey was designed to give us a high-level overview of the sorts of respondents who were engaging with the subsequent questions. The questions in survey section 1 were designed to be as accessible as possible in order to encourage the respondent to continue with the survey. With hindsight, some of the questions could have been more helpfully designed for ease of subsequent analysis by limiting respondents' answering options, but we are generally pleased to have received so many responses, to have heard from a healthy variety of countries around the world and to have managed to contact digital preservation practitioners from a range of organisation types and sizes.

The survey responses can therefore enrich EDEN's understanding of the seven discipline-specific early adopter disciplines on which WP3 is focusing. These are derived from the seven discipline areas (Climate Simulations; Earth and Environmental Sciences; Food Sciences; High-Energy Physics; Life Sciences and Bioinformatics; Linguistics; and Social Sciences)²⁶ represented by repositories participating in the EDEN project.

The survey takes discipline-specific and discipline-agnostic data preservation into consideration and this minimises risk of an unintentionally narrow discipline-specific focus.

Taking each subsection's most popular response, our most frequently reported characteristics are:

- Role: a digital preservation practitioner working directly with research data objects;

²⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17293244>

- Setting: working in a medium to large-sized European archive²⁷ or university library²⁸ setting;
- Discipline: whose collection has no specific discipline focus but serves multiple disciplines.

Of course this does not fit all respondents, but as a reflection of the most frequently-reported characteristics, this is an unsurprising profile that provides a reassuring validity check. It may also suggest that engaging with outliers, i.e. those respondents who do not fit this profile, may be an interesting route for follow-up interviews.

5.2 Survey section 2: Frameworks and guidelines for long-term digital preservation

Questions in survey section 2 explore the standards, guidelines and frameworks—in other words, the reference documents—that are currently used by digital preservation practitioners in their day-to-day work; and investigate working definitions of 'long-term' in the preservation context.

5.2.1 Frameworks and guidelines for identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation

In question 2.1, we move from identifying the respondent's profile to understanding the range of existing frameworks, guidelines and standards that are currently in use in their daily digital preservation work, particularly relating to the identification, appraisal and selection of data.

The design and presentation of this question is discussed in report section 2.3.2, above, but to recap: we presented respondents with a list of guidelines, frameworks and standards that have been generated through consultation and desk research. We asked each respondent to indicate whether they had 'heard of and currently use' the document, 'heard of but do not currently use' the document, or 'have not heard of' the document.

5.2.1.1 Responses across all guidelines/frameworks/standards

In Table 6 ([Appendix B](#)), the full response to each guideline/framework/standard is presented. These are provided in order of most frequently to least frequently used, as indicated by the choice of response "Heard of, and currently use", but the table contains all three possible responses for each framework.

The following figure (Figure 15) provides a succinct view of responses to this question. (Please note that in the survey tool, the names of guidelines, frameworks and standards were presented in full; they are presented in the figure in an abbreviated form due to the space constraints of the figure.)

²⁷ Using analysis by organisation class (rather than org type).

²⁸ Using analysis by organisation type (rather than org class).

Figure 15: Knowledge and use of guidelines, standards and frameworks per guideline/standard/framework.

Here and in Table 6 ([Appendix B](#)), we see that institutional frameworks (i.e. the institutional preservation policy and the collection development policy/statement/strategy) and conceptual frameworks about digital data object handling (i.e. OAIS and the FAIR Principles) are the most commonly known and used frameworks among respondents. Implementation standards such as PREMIS and certification frameworks like CoreTrustSeal are less popular with our respondents.

5.2.1.2 Responses by individual guideline/standard/framework

It is useful to also have a view of the use of individual guidelines, frameworks and standards. Below, we present the reaction to the most popular reference documents individually, each of them being used by at least half of the respondents.

The following diagrams (Figures 16-21) compare the levels of knowledge and use of the 6 most widely adopted frameworks among different organisation classes (in relative numbers), giving a sense of trends among the diverse organisational landscape working in digital preservation.

Figure 16: Knowledge and use of institutional preservation policy, by organisation class.

Figure 17: Knowledge and use of institutional collection policy/statement/strategy, by organisation class.

Figure 18: Knowledge and use of ISO 14721 OAIS, by organisation class.

Figure 19: Knowledge and use of the FAIR Guiding Principles, by organisation class.

Figure 20: Knowledge and use of PREMIS, by organisation class.

Figure 21: Knowledge and use of CoreTrustSeal, by organisation class.

5.2.1.3 Responses by usage level

For ease of reference, we also collected the responses to each of the three usage answer options (i.e. “Heard of and currently use”, “Heard of but do not currently use”, and “Have not heard of”) across all standards/frameworks/guidelines.

In Figure 22 below and Table 7 ([Appendix B](#)), we see the various answering options ranked by frequency of response, "Heard of, and currently use".

Figure 22: Knowledge and use of guidelines and frameworks per guideline/framework, ranked by ‘Heard of and currently use’ (shown in green).

In Figure 23 below and Table 8 ([Appendix B](#)), we see the suggested guidelines, standards and frameworks ranked from most to least frequent responses of, "Heard of but do not currently use".

Figure 23: Knowledge and use of guidelines and frameworks per guideline/framework, ranked by "Heard of but do not currently use".

Finally in Figure 24 below and Table 9 (Appendix B), we see the least well-known suggested guidelines or frameworks, ranked by frequency of response, "Have not heard of".

Figure 24: Knowledge and use of guidelines and frameworks per guideline/framework, ranked from most to least by response "Have not heard of".

As shown in Figure 22 above (and Table 7), the institutional preservation policy is very widely reported as the key framework or guideline in use. The OAIS reference model also enjoys a high

level of awareness, as do the FAIR Principles. These three documents appeared at the bottom of Figure 24 (i.e. *least* likely to be unheard of), validating our findings.

We hope the findings from this section are of use particularly to those who are involved in the creation, management or promotion of these key reference documents.

5.2.1.4 'Other' frameworks, standards or guidelines

We asked respondents to tell us about any other framework, standard or guideline that they have heard of or use, where that framework, standard or guideline has not been offered as a choice in the survey. This was primarily to find any themes emerging from the frameworks, standards or guidelines suggested here by respondents: i.e., if there were any documents that were mentioned more than once, that would constitute a meaningful omission from our list of suggestions.

"Other framework, standard or guideline that you may have heard of or use" was chosen by 39 respondents. These respondents were invited to provide more information on this response, and supplied the following rich list of 22 items, quoted here as entered unless otherwise indicated by square brackets:

- ADDML <https://www.arkivverket.no/forvaltning-og-utvikling/regelverk-og-standarder>
- DIAS <https://www.arkivverket.no/forvaltning-og-utvikling/regelverk-og-standarder>
- Digital Streams Matrix <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.26363> - a supporting document to the Digital Stewardship End-to-End Workflow Model found in publication <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.34317>
- Digital Stewardship Appraisal Framework <https://osf.io/sezpj/>
- DINI-Certificate for Repositories
- DPC RAM and Handbook
- Dublin Core Initiative [sic]
- FADGI
- Global Open Science Cloud framework
- IASA guidelines for audiovisual preservation <https://www.iasa-web.org/tc04/audio-preservation>
- Requirements and guidelines that include retention and archiving of GxP data, e.g. ICH E6(R3)
- Library of Congress' METS and MODS
- NDSA's Levels of Digital Preservation <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>
- NOARK <https://www.arkivverket.no/forvaltning-og-utvikling/regelverk-og-standarder>
- PRONOM format registry
- scoremodel.org
- SIARD <https://www.arkivverket.no/forvaltning-og-utvikling/regelverk-og-standarder>
- [U.S.] Federal Agencies Digital Guidelines Initiative
- U.S. National Archives and Records Administration Digital Preservation Framework <https://github.com/usnationalarchives/digital-preservation>
- V&A Born-Digital Decision Model <https://vanda-production-assets.s3.amazonaws.com/2022/04/26/16/37/4>

Each choice in this list was chosen by one respondent.

We noted with interest that many of these standards are more applicable at a process-specific level of digital object handling for specific content types (like FADGI or SIARD) or for metadata (i.e., METS / MODS and Dublin Core) while we were—as stated—focusing more on standards that help inform identification, appraisal and selection. This left us wondering: Do people use these for selection / identification / appraisal - or did they just want to tell us other standards that they use?

5.2.2 Defining ‘long-term’ in the context of digital preservation

The concept of ‘long-term’ in the context of digital preservation often arises in the guidelines, frameworks and standards discussed in the previous survey question, and as a key concept in the inquiry described by this report. We realised it would therefore be important to examine this concept in more detail in order to understand, first of all, how widely ‘long-term’ is defined at all in practice; and then secondly, in the cases where it is defined, whether these definitions vary.

5.2.2.1 Existence of a definition

Question 2.2 asked participants whether they had an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ preservation in use in their organisational setting. Respondents were asked to choose one option only. Results are shown in Figure 25 below and Table 10 ([Appendix B](#)).

Figure 25: Existence of definition of ‘long-term’ in the digital preservation context.

We can see here that a slight majority of respondents (n=130, 52%) do have an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ in their organisation. Conversely, we note the large minority of those who are working with no agreed definition of ‘long-term’.

We broke this down further by organisation class, ranked by frequency of the ‘no’ response in Figure 26 below.

Figure 26: Existence of definition of “long-term” - org classes sorted by frequency of ‘no’.

We see that the organisation class with the most respondents working without an agreed definition of ‘long-term’ is the ‘Museum or gallery’ class followed by ‘Library’ and then, surprisingly perhaps, ‘Digital preservation service’.

5.2.2.2 ‘Long-term’ definition: yes

Of those who answered “yes” to the question “In your organisation, do you have an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ in the context of digital preservation?” (52%, n=130), the subsidiary question asked the respondent to then supply that definition. These responses were qualitatively analysed (see [Appendix C](#)) to identify any themes that arose.

The most common working definition of ‘long-term’ in the preservation context was “forever”, “as long as possible”, or another expression of an unlimited period of time (n=35). The second most common was a minimum period of ten years (n=30). Other responses had much lower popularity: 7 responses defined long-term as being that in which the material outlasts obsolescence of various kinds (technological change or obsolescence had 6 mentions and legal or administrative obsolescence had 1 mention); a minimum period of 100 years was chosen by 6 responses; a minimum period of 50 years was chosen by 5 respondents; 4 respondents chose “as long as the organisational lifetime” or equivalent phraseology; and 2 further responses indicated “until the objects are selected for deletion”.

A further response was worth noting: 9 respondents specifically brought up the importance of object accessibility and usability—usually in conjunction with their various stated minimum timeframes. These responses emphasised the point that an agreed minimum timeframe should

specifically be an indication of the timeframe for which objects are available and accessible by users (in addition to being preserved). This idea was poetically expressed by this response:

"An archive without its users is merely a desolate repository for information that is never accessed."

This type of response indicates that we are tapping into the priorities of digital preservationists (in this case, a practitioner from a medium-sized archive) who care deeply about the objects that they preserve being as accessible, findable and reusable as possible.

5.2.2.3 'Long-term' definition: no

When being asked about the existence of a working definition of 'long-term', respondents could of course alternatively respond "no". We asked such respondents (44.8%, n=112) to elaborate on why, in their opinion, there is no such definition at their organisation. Respondents were able to choose more than one answer.

As can be seen from Figure 27 below, and Table 11 ([Appendix B](#)), the most frequent response amongst those without an existing definition was that consensus had not yet been achieved on a definition (n=41). The two most frequent responses after this were that a definition is planned or in progress (n=36), and another reason to be detailed in the text box supplied (n=35). Finally seven respondents noted that their organisation does not do what they define as 'long-term' preservation. Eight respondents chose more than one answer; the remainder chose a single response.

Figure 27: Overview of reasons for lack of agreed or working definition of 'long-term'.

When "Other reason" was chosen here, respondents were invited to provide more information. We present the codes applied to these textual responses in Table 12, below. Responses were qualitatively coded to themes and codes presented in the order of most to least frequent.

Table 12: Other reasons for lack of agreed or working definition of 'long term': analysis of responses to 'Other reason'.

"Please specify the other reason that you do not currently have an agreed or working definition of "long-term" in the context of digital preservation": response codes.	<i>n</i>
There is indeed a working understanding of 'long-term', and that it equates to 'as long as necessary/possible' (<i>respondent should have reported this as 'yes' to top-line question 2.2.</i>)	10
Reiteration that there is no working definition	5
Creating a definition is not our responsibility	3
Due to confusion/disorganisation/organisation is in transition	3
Current intention to take action to develop an agreed or working definition (<i>N.B: "A definition is planned or in progress" was one of the answering options offered in the previous question</i>)	3
Due to funding issues	2
Because a definition is not needed	2
We use definitions from standards/funders (but do not supply these definitions here)	2
Due to difficulty getting agreement (<i>"We have not yet achieved consensus" was one of the answering options offered in the previous question</i>)	1
Because there is no drive at the organisation to achieve this	1
Because it is not our highest priority	1
The definition varies by collection	1
I don't know whether a definition exists or not.	1

Here we see that many respondents (n=10) chose to characterise their current situation as being *without* an agreed or working definition of 'long-term' whilst also reporting that there *is* actually a working definition after all, and that that working definition is 'as long as necessary/possible' or equivalent. Perhaps for these respondents, this is judged to be a presumption or an unspoken perception of a definition of 'long-term' that they are unsure is shared by colleagues, and thus does not qualify as an "agreed definition". Our wording of question 2.2 with the deliberate use of the term "working definition" was deliberately designed to capture these informal, unspoken or tacit understandings of definitions, but clearly here 10 respondents were sufficiently unsure of a shared understanding of the definition that they use, to report it as a non-existent definition.

In addition, many respondents (n=5) simply reiterated here the fact that there is not an agreed or working definition at their organisation, rather than supplying the requested reason for this lack.

More interestingly, however, we also see that there were several reports of no definition at the respondent's organisation because the creation of a definition is not the responsibility of the respondent or their team, or that the lack of definition is due to confusion, disorganisation, or a period of transition at the organisation. There were also several reports that funding has caused difficulties in this area—either directly in supporting the work required to agree a definition, or in the creation or maintenance of preservation infrastructure which would require a definition to exist. This may be an interesting area for further interviewing.

A couple of other responses flatly denied that a definition of 'long-term' was even necessary:

“We have not discussed the issue as there really is no need to define everything.”

“Never felt the need to define.”

This perspective, however, is very much in the minority.

5.2.3 Survey section 2: reflections

These results may indicate that 'long-term' in the digital preservation context, whilst being a widely used term (not least by the EOSC Long-Term Data Preservation Task Force²⁹, the EOSC Long-Term Data Retention Task Force³⁰, and within EDEN), is not a consistently defined concept across the sector. Definitions of 'long-term' are inconsistently available from organisation to organisation, with almost half of our respondents reporting no existing definition within their organisation; and those definitions that do exist vary dramatically in the length of time that 'long-term' represents. This means that the digital preservation world is frequently using a shared term underpinned by—in some cases—markedly different presumptions. This points to an interesting area for further examination.

Questioning around the definition of 'long-term' in the context of digital preservation practice and policy yielded some interesting possible avenues for future interviews. For example, a number of respondents reported that they had no existing definition, but in fact actually do have a working definition of long-term which they reported as 'as long as possible/necessary'. It would be useful to explore further with these respondents how this tacit understanding came about and how confident they are that it is or is not shared with colleagues. It would also be interesting to find out more about how funding affects activity in this area; and to investigate with those who reported a definition was not their responsibility, where they consider responsibility to lie.

It was also interesting to note the existing connections between the digital preservation realm and what is currently designated FAIR data, which was evidenced by the discussion introduced by respondents about the importance of ongoing findability and access, whatever the preservation period. This reminds us that many of the ideas now encapsulated in the FAIR Principles have been, to some extent, bedrocks of preservation practice for years. It may be interesting for those engaged in training to explore the extent to which digital preservation practitioners are already

²⁹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

³⁰ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

engaging with the principles and sub-principles of FAIR data. It could also potentially be interesting, as a follow-on activity, to analyse the content of the guidelines found to be popular in survey section 2 in order to understand the overlap with the concerns of the FAIR Principles. This could be a useful further specification of the existing work in this area (for example, the 2021 paper from Currie and Kilbride³¹, the CESSDA Data Archiving Guide³², etc.)

In terms of interesting further analysis, it may be worthwhile undertaking further research on trends for different frameworks per organisation class, or examining whether an organisation class with a noticeably low or high rate of “yes” for the existence of a definition correlates with a high or low rate of “yes” for certain frameworks.

5.3 Survey section 3: Current practices in identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation

Questions in survey section 3 focus more closely upon current practices in identification, appraisal and selection of data for long-term digital preservation. Here we dig further into the nuts and bolts of the identification, appraisal and selection workflow over time, including how digital objects enter the organisation; whether and how they are assessed at the point of ingest; whether they are reassessed during the preservation life-cycle; what the initial preservation period for digital objects is when those objects have been selected for ‘long-term’ preservation; and what happens to them after this initial preservation period has ended.

5.3.1 How digital data objects for preservation usually enter the organisation

We asked respondents to define how the preservation life-cycle usually begins, by asking how digital data objects for preservation usually enter the organisation. Responses are listed in Figure 28 below and Table 13 ([Appendix B](#)).

The intention here was to get a sense of the most frequent single route by which digital data objects for preservation arrive at the organisation. We can see that the most frequently-reported way that digital data objects arrive at the organisation, across all responses, is as a result of voluntary self-deposit by the researcher.

However, as respondents were able to select more than one answer, we next looked at different combinations of ways that data objects enter the organisation.

³¹ <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v16i1.768>

³² <https://dag.CESSDA.eu/Chapter-5/1-Introduction-to-FAIR#>

Figure 28: Most common acquisition strategies³³ across all responses, ranked by most to least frequent.

Figure 29, below, provides a heat map of the correlation between different ways in which objects enter the organisation. Among organisations with multiple acquisition strategies, ‘Self-deposit’ and ‘Funder-mandated deposit’, as well as ‘Proactive monitoring/harvesting’ and ‘Proactive monitoring/invitations’ tend to go hand-in-hand, in forming a common acquisition strategy cluster. Most correlations involving ‘Parent-organisation deposit’ are very weak (0.00–0.11). This suggests that ‘Parent-organisation’ deposits may be independent of other strategies.

³³ “Acquisition strategy” is being used here as a shorthand to mean the way or ways in which a given organisation receives, solicits or otherwise brings about the entry of digital data objects to the organisation. We recognise that sometimes this process is initiated by the data producer, and sometimes by the organisation (and sometimes by someone else). Our conceptualisation of the acquisition strategy may involve aspects of identification and selection, but is prior to any formal selection or appraisal process carried out by the organisation at ingest. An alternative shorthand term could have been “reception strategy”, “arrival strategy” or similar; the priority was to maintain a conceptual clarity from the formal ingest process.

	Self-deposit by researcher on a voluntary basis	Funder-mandated deposit by researcher	Depositors are identified and invited to submit their data (<i>Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring</i>)	Harvesting of data objects (<i>Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring</i>)	Parent-organisation deposit	Third party data preservation collaboration
Self-deposit by researcher on a voluntary basis						
Funder-mandated deposit by researcher	0,44					
Depositors are identified and invited to submit their data (<i>Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring</i>)	0,05	0,03				
Harvesting of data objects (<i>Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring</i>)	-0,04	-0,07	0,40			
Parent-organisation deposit	0,04	0,00	0,05	0,05		
Third party data preservation collaboration	0,09	0,19	0,14	0,08	0,11	

Figure 29: Heat map of correlation between different routes by which data objects enter the organisation. For legibility we note here the labels of the X axis from left to right, and the Y axis from top to bottom. These labels are, in order: Self-deposit by researcher on a voluntary basis; Funder-mandated deposit by researcher; Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring: depositors are identified and invited to submit their data; Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring: harvesting of data objects; Parent-organisation deposit; Third party data preservation collaboration. Description of the colours: Negative correlation (yellow; -1): mostly do not appear together; No distinct correlation (grey; 0): No linear relationship; Positive correlation (turquoise; 1): appear together quite often.

Overall, we interpret these responses to mean that here, respondents are reporting the *various routes by which they often receive data objects*, rather than strictly reporting on the *single most common* (“usual”) route alone. This latter meaning was what was requested by the survey question. However it appears that, in order to get an accurate response to the *usual* (i.e. the sole most frequent) route by which objects arrive, we would have needed to have made the wording of this question clearer on this point, and also made this question open to one response only.

For further clarity on the overall distribution of multiple vs. single acquisition strategies among all responses, as well as the relative popularity of various single strategies, please see Figure 30.

Figure 30: Most common acquisition strategies among all responses including breakdown of single strategies.

Next, in Figure 31, we characterised the routes by which organisation classes receive objects as either a single (one reported route, selected from the provided options) or multiple (more than one reported route, selected from the provided options) acquisition strategy.

Figure 31: Acquisition strategies by organisation class.

Figure 31 shows that most organisations either follow a single or multiple acquisition strategy, selected from the provided options, except for the ‘Archive’ class which employs more complex ways of acquisition as evidenced by the high number of “Other” (i.e. open text) responses.

This also stands out in the following net diagrams (Figure 32a and b), which provide a comparative overview of how different organisation classes indicated their most common acquisition strategies. Due to the number of datasets, we split the visualisation into two diagrams for legibility.

Figure 32a: Different routes by which data objects usually enter the organisation, by organisation class. See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig_32a_Acquisition_Strategies.png](#)

Figure 32b: Different routes by which data objects usually enter the organisation, by organisation class. See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig 32b Acquisition Strategies.png](#)

The net diagrams (in Figure 32a and b) indicate that archives appear to have a distinct approach to acquisition strategy. All other organisation classes report high levels of ‘self-deposit’, followed by ‘funder-mandated deposit’ as the second-highest reported acquisition route, whereas archives predominantly acquire objects by deposit as a result of active monitoring (depositors are identified and invited to submit their data) with ‘parent-organisation deposit’ and ‘self-deposit’ being in equal second place (n=26 each).

Since the org class ‘Archive’ makes up about a quarter of all responses, it is important to note that any assumptions drawn from the overall analysis of these responses may be affected by this strong representation of responses from archives.

Thirty-four of those 55 responses that included the option "Other - please specify", used this "Other" option along with various combinations of other available answering options, rather than choosing "Other" as a sole response, as was intended. This strengthens the conclusion that we should have obliged respondents to choose one answer only here, as does the fact that most respondents entered a large amount of textual commentary in the open text field, elaborating on the various different ways that objects arrive, used to arrive, or may arrive in the future—much of which relates to the other answering options chosen—which presented additional challenges to the analyst.

Nineteen responses selected "Other" alone. It is only in the 18 textual responses provided (i.e. one respondent selected “Other” but then did not supply a textual response) that we can see clearly the variety of additional routes by which objects arrive. These are listed here exactly as input:

- All data are public available online at [link].
- Legislative mandate - government agencies are meant to transfer records appraised as 'National Archives' to us
- All public record creators have an obligation to transfer their material selected for preservation to the National Archives or other specifically designated institutions under the Public Records Act of 1968.
- Digital data objects find their way to the National Archive because of the Archive Law. Objects are exported from Provider systems and imported into our repository.
- Because of legal requirements (Bundesarchivgesetz)
- Deposit as a result of legal obligation
- Records to be archived are identified in appraisal decisions. Government agencies are legally obliged to transfer records that have been assigned permanent value as part of national heritage to the National Archives. We also receive transfers from private archives (e.g. private persons, organizations and associations).
- all data are records of the administration
- donations by staff or donors
- By donation or bequeathment - we are an Archive.
- Digitization of library materials
- From different departments throughout the whole company.
- They are entering the Organization by the policy of the archive-law.
- clients are using the shibboleth-entering to their mandatory deposit in DIMAG
- The digital records are produced in the course of my institution's activities, through systems used for the creation of digital judicial cases, for example. My department is responsible for classifying, appraising, and assigning disposition to these cases in accordance with the Records Retention Schedule.
- We're not currently equipped to accept transfers of digital data (we're working on it!), however when we're up and running, we'll use "Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring -

depositors will be invited/required to submit their data. Currently most of our digital material is acquired through the digitisation of hard copy material in the collections.

- through the organization’s own internal processes
- Digital objects created by the organization while executing its mandate through its various departmental functions based on existing retention policy. There are also external digital objects which are either seized or voluntarily given to the organizations in the execution of its mandate.

As can be seen from this list, few responses actually present us with an alternative route by which objects arrive; most of these responses discuss other aspects of the data objects received by the organisation. However, we can still identify a few themes from these responses: a) organisational legal mandate is a recurring additional route for object deposit, along with b) deposit, bequest or seizure (!) from non-researcher donors.

5.3.2 Assessment of quality of digital data objects at point of ingest

Respondents were asked whether quality assessment checks are carried out at the point of ingest of digital data objects for long-term preservation. Answering responses offered specification of 5 different ‘yes’ options for different types of quality check, plus ‘no’ and ‘I don’t know’. More than one response could be chosen. An overview of ‘yes’ / ‘no’ / ‘I don’t know’ responses is provided in Figure 33 and Table 14 ([Appendix B](#)).

Figure 33: Quality assessments at ingest: overview of responses.

We also broke down the responses to this question by organisation class (see Figure 34).

Figure 34: Quality assessment at ingest, broken down by organisation class.

More detailed information (i.e., beyond ‘yes’, ‘no’ and ‘I don’t know’) on what kind of quality checks are performed at ingest, is listed—from most to least popular—in Table 14 ([Appendix B](#)).

It seems clear that the majority of respondents do carry out quality checks of some kind at the point of ingest. Descriptive metadata (n=174) and administrative metadata (n=170) are frequently examined at point of ingest, with slightly lower frequency reported for the checking of technical quality of the data (n=161) and quality of the technical metadata (n=159). Checking for the content/information quality of the data is the type of check at ingest with the lowest reported frequency (n=144), but all the suggested types of checking at ingest occur in more than 50% of responses.

The most frequently mentioned quality checks at point of ingest, across all respondents, are shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Most frequently mentioned quality assessments of data objects at ingest.

We then examined the different types of quality check performed on the objects at ingest, separated out by organisation class (Figure 36a and b). Due to the number of datasets, we split the visualisation into two diagrams for legibility. As can be seen here, organisation classes mostly follow a similar pattern, employing all the quality checks that we suggested with only occasional variations in emphasis.

The organisation type “Museum or gallery”, however, stands out by exhibiting low values for the checking of i) technical quality; ii) descriptive metadata quality; and iii) administrative metadata quality. Among the 11 participants from the “Museum or gallery” organisation class, only 4 indicated checking technical quality and the quality of administrative metadata; only 6 respondents checked quality of descriptive metadata. By doing so, the class demonstrates a noticeably different pattern of quality checking routines than the others.

Figure 36a: Types of quality checks performed at ingest, by organisation class. See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig_36a_Quality_Checks_Ingest.png](#)

Figure 36b: Types of quality checks performed at ingest, by organisation class. See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig_36b_Quality_Checks_Ingest.png](#)

We then further examined, separately, how respondents went about assessing the **technical** quality and the **content/information** quality of data objects, as these two types of check can be understood and undertaken in a variety of different ways.

5.3.2.1 Technical quality checks of data objects at ingest

Figure 37 shows the overview of responses regarding whether or not technical quality checks are undertaken at ingest.

Figure 37: Technical quality checks undertaken at ingest: overview of responses.

We can see here that a clear majority of respondents do indeed assess the technical quality of data objects at the point of interest.

Figure 38, below, and Table 15 ([Appendix B](#)) shows the types of technical quality checks (e.g. correct rendering, conforming to standard specifications) undertaken by respondents at the point of ingest. Results show only responses from those who reported 'yes', i.e. that they perform technical quality checks of data objects at ingest.

Figure 38: Popularity of types of technical quality checks at ingest (of 'yes' responses).

Here in Figure 38 we see file format identification as clearly the most popular assessment undertaken of technical quality of the data, as 93.2% of those who report that they carry out technical quality checks at ingest, reported performing file format identification. This was followed by integrity checking at 84.5%, file format validation at 77.6%, visual inspection at 73.3%, virus checking at 70.2% and normalisation/migration at 55.9%. Respondents could select more than one response.

Figure 39: Occurrence of technical quality checks at ingest, sorted by org class.

In Figure 39, we examine “yes” responses (i.e. that technical checks are performed at ingest) by organisation class. This shows that ‘Repository’ is the org class with the highest reported rate of technical quality check at the point of ingest, with a noticeably higher rate than all other org classes.

We saw in Figure 38 that an answering option is an “Other” type of technical check undertaken upon data (not metadata) at ingest. Six respondents chose “Other” and were invited to describe these “other” technical quality checks. Responses are listed here, as they were entered in the text box provided:

- Copy right checking, data quality checking, data curation (data paper) compatible checking, scientific ethic principle checking, data security and regulation requirement checking,
- Digital content not already in the collection should go through a basic Quality Control (QC) checking process and a condition assessment should be undertaken, resulting in a Condition Report (at present this is an interim document). Tools used at present include DROID, ExifTool and MediaInfo. As we are only beginning to design workflows, a 'bare minimum' process is undertaken at present.
- Metadata format conformity
- appraisal via emulation
- Access
- The processes are not yet developed, so we can't answer this yet.

Most responses here talk more broadly about the checking process in general (or the lack of one) rather than technical quality checks on data (rather than metadata) specifically. Responses that do address the technical quality of the data include data security and regulation requirement checking;

condition assessment using DROID, Exiftool, and MediaInfo; and appraisal via emulation (1 response each). Two responses noted that their workflow has not yet been designed.

The following 2 figures (see Figure 40 and 41 below) visualise the trends identified. Due to the number of datasets, we split the visualisation into two diagrams for legibility. We decided to group GLAM institutions and the overarching classes “Multifunctional” and “Digital preservation service” into Figure 40, and show organisations operating in a more traditional research environment in Figure 41.

Figure 40: Types of assessment of technical quality at ingest (GLAM and multifunctional organisations). See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig 40 Technical Quality 1.png](#)

Figure 41: Types of assessment of technical quality at ingest (research environment organisations). See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig 41 Technical Quality II.png](#)

Here, we see that performing integrity checking, file format identification, file format validation and visual inspections are more or less common practices among all org classes, with minor variations. Virus checking seems to be less common overall.

There is also a notable variation in the employment of normalisation which seems to be popular in some domains (i.e. Archive, Research performing organisation) but is less common in most other org classes (in particular, for Research infrastructures).

5.3.2.2 Content/information quality checks of data objects at ingest

We also asked respondents to discuss the checks undertaken at ingest of the **content/information** quality of their data objects (not metadata). Responses are reported in Figure 42 below. Full responses are noted in Table 16 ([Appendix B](#)).

Figure 42: Whether content/information quality checks are undertaken at ingest.

Here we see that a majority of respondents report that their organisation does assess the content/information quality of data objects at the point of ingest.

We then analyse this further by organisation class (see Figure 43). This shows that archives and the 'Museum or gallery' category are noticeably more likely to carry out checks on content/information quality at ingest, than the other organisation classes. With those who answered "yes", we then looked more closely at the types of check performed, based on the respondent choices from a range of options (see Figure 44). Our results show that provenance, completeness and documentation were all checked by more than 50% of "yes" responses.

We then examined the types of checks on content/information quality which are carried out by the different organisation classes (see Figures 45 and 46). Here again, we see the archives organisation class exhibiting different behaviour from the other organisation classes, with more checking activity reported overall and in particularly high levels of checking for provenance, completeness and documentation. In Figure 45, we particularly see a noticeably high incidence of checking of provenance by museum/gallery respondents - which is to be expected - and in Figure 46 we see noticeably high level of checking of documentation by repositories; both these results stand in contrast to other check behaviors and also the activity of other organisation types.

Figure 43: Whether content/information quality checks are undertaken at ingest, broken down by organisation class.

Figure 44: Types of quality check of content/information quality at ingest (of 'yes' responses), from most to least frequent.

Figure 45: Types of check of content/information quality carried out at ingest, by organisation class (GLAM and multifunctional organisations). See a larger version of this image online here:

[Fig_45_Content_Quality_1.png](#)

Figure 46: Types of check of content/information quality carried out at ingest, by organisation class (research environment organisations). See a larger version of this image online here: [Fig 46 Content Quality II.png](#)

Again, we gathered the "other" responses to this question, which were (again) a mixed bag, including responses relating to technical quality and to metadata. These responses are listed here as entered:

- functionality and error
- Collection criteria
- i know this is done, but i do not do this personally
- in compliance with standardised thesaurustermes
- author and co-authors, affilications, funding information, geogrpahical resolutions or scales, by-langgude compatible checking (Chinese and English), maps and figures, datasets with data papers compatible checking
- Descriptive metadata (that a minimum amount of descriptive information is provided or available).
- data compliance
- analysis of file directories. appraisal and access via emulation
- well structured, good metadata, long term usability (no special programs needed. Open formats preferred).

Some of these comments (e.g. descriptive metadata; data compliance; analysis of file directories; well structured, good metadata) could be interpreted as being primarily concerned with compliance with minimal preservation requirements.

5.3.3 Reassessment of quality of preserved digital data objects

So far, our interest in technical checks and content/information quality checks has been focused on checks carried out at the point of ingest. Our next inquiry was whether respondents perform a regular **reassessment** of the quality of their preserved data objects, i.e. at regular moments during the agreed preservation period.

As can be seen from Figure 47 and [Table 17](#), most respondents reported that no regular reassessment is performed.

Figure 47: Occurrence of reassessment of quality.

Sixty-nine respondents, however, selected “yes”, and were asked to specify how frequently this reassessment happens via a free text box. Answers are noted in Table 18 below, in order of popularity.

Table 18: Frequency of reassessment of quality of preserved digital data objects.

Frequency of recurring checks	<i>n</i>
Annually	15
It varies	14
On demand	7
Monthly	5
Every 5 to 9 years	4
Every 10 to 19 years	3
Continuously/daily	3
Quarterly	3
Schedule is in planning/under discussion	3
Every two years	2
Every 20 years +	1
Every four years	1
Every three years	1
Twice per year/every six months	1
Every two months	1
I don't know	1

We can see here that an annual pattern ($n=15$) is, unsurprisingly, very common among those who carry out regular checks, with the next most common regular pattern being monthly at a significantly lower level of popularity ($n=5$). After “annually”, the next most popular schedule for recurring checks of preserved objects are “it varies” ($n=14$) and “on demand” ($n=7$)—neither of which are regular schedules of checking but, conversely, represent *ad hoc* checking strategies.

5.3.4 Respondents who define LTP, perform checks at ingest and perform reassessment

We looked for responses where the organisation i) has a long-term definition; AND ii) performs quality checks at the point of ingest; AND iii) performs re-assessments of quality of digital objects at later stages in the preservation period. Examination of respondents who have reported activity in all of these three measures allows us to investigate potential trends of where these high measures of activity occur. Overall, 18.8% ($n=47$) of all respondents meet these criteria.

As can be seen in Table 19 below, re-assessment routines within this group are most common for ‘Museums or gallery’ and ‘Library’ classes, whereas it is less common for archives and digital preservation services, i.e. about third of all ‘Museum or gallery’ and ‘Library’ respondents have an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ and perform multiple quality checks at ingest and during the preservation period; whereas among the archives respondents, only around a sixth do that.

A further - perhaps surprising point was that 6 of 7 responses from digital preservation service providers indicated that they do not perform re-assessments.

Table 19: Percentage per org class that indicated a) having a definition of long-term; b) performing quality checks at point of ingest; and c) re-assessments at later stage.

Org class	% reporting LTP definition + ingest checks + reassessments
Museum or gallery	35.7
Library	31.0
Unassigned	27.3
Archive	16.4
Digital preservation service	14.3
Multifunctional	13.3
Research infrastructure	7.7
Repository	5.9
Research performing organisation	5.9

5.3.5 Initial preservation period for digital data objects

In order to validate the discussion around definitions of 'long-term', we asked what, in practice, is the initial preservation period to which the respondent's organisation commits, for data objects that have been selected for 'long-term' preservation.

Responses are available in Figure 48 and in Table 20, ranked by decreasing length of time.

Figure 48: Distribution of reported initial preservation commitment (in years).

Table 20: Length of initial preservation commitment (in years).

For how long do you initially preserve digital data objects that have been selected for "long-term" digital preservation? This applies to your usual practice where no special conditions or contracts apply. Please answer in years.	n	Ratio (of 250)
100	81	32.4%
99	1	0.4%
75	1	0.4%
60	1	0.4%
50	9	3.6%
40	2	0.8%
30	3	1.2%
25	4	1.6%
22	1	0.4%
20	9	3.6%
15	4	1.6%
10	53	21.2%

5	4	1.6%
3	2	0.8%
2	1	0.4%
1	1	0.4%
No answer	73	29.2%

There is a predictable popularity reported here for a stated initial preservation period of 100 years (n=81) which seems to function here as a proxy for "forever" or equivalent terminology. This is consistent with trends reported in the definitions of 'long-term' in report section 5.2.2.

The next most popular initial preservation period reported is 10 years (n=53). Whilst all other stated periods are significantly less popular, there are a couple of surprising stated lengths including 22 years (n=1) and four respondents reported that the initial 'long-term' preservation period was less than five years. We note the relatively high level of "no answer" responses and reflect on this in section 5.3.7, below.

5.3.6 What happens to objects after the initial preservation period

We followed up with questioning about the initial preservation period, by asking what happens once that period comes to an end. Results are reported in Table 21, from most to least frequent.

Table 21: What happens to digital data objects after the initial preservation period.

Once the initial "long-term" preservation period has ended, what usually happens to digital data objects?	n	Ratio (of 250)
We take no specific action.	98	39.20%
I don't know.	48	19.20%
We do something else at the end of the initial preservation period.	38	15.20%
We consult the depositor to agree on the next steps.	32	12.80%
No Answer.	29	11.60%
We return the data to the depositor and delete our copy.	3	1.20%
We delete the data, without consulting the depositor.	2	0.80%

The majority of respondents ("We take no specific action" plus "I don't know", totalling 146 responses of 250) were not able to describe a specific action that happens at the end of the initial preservation period. The most common definite response, excluding "we take no specific action", "I don't know", and "we do something else", was to consult the depositor to agree on next steps (n=32). Five more respondents offered other specific action steps: 3 respondents return data to the depositor and delete the preserved copy: and 2 further respondents delete the data without consulting the depositor.

There was a relatively high number of “something else” responses (n=38). These were coded to 6 themes that emerged from this data, as seen in Table 22 below. As can be seen by the numbers here, some responses were coded to more than one theme. An example follows:

“We preserve data indefinitely or until the responsible organization asks for it to be deleted or returned to them. There is no ‘initial period’.”

This example was coded to: ‘We continue to preserve’ and ‘We reject notion of initial period’. (Please see [Appendix C](#) for the full text responses and the qualitative coding assigned.)

Table 22: What happens to digital data objects after the conclusion of the initial preservation period: “something else” responses.

Please specify what happens to data after the initial "long-term" preservation period (other responses).	n	Ratio (of 38)
We continue to preserve	20	52.6%
We consult with depositor	8	21.1%
We re-evaluate value of retention	7	18.4%
We transfer the digital data objects elsewhere	4	10.5%
We reject notion of an "initial period"	2	5.3%
We are currently designing process	1	2.6%

We hoped these responses would help explain the slightly low response rate and indeed they did: many respondents (n=20) wanted to highlight that they view their preservation work as ongoing, and that the preservation period would be longer than 100 years. For example:

“Our definition of "long-term" reaches way longer than only 100 years. We keep them.”

“We preserve data that we own so preserve to infinity. Or until we change our preservation or collection policies...”

Rather than choose the option “we take no specific action”, these respondents chose the “something else” option to flag this point. On reflection, we realise that this may be an indication that respondents view continued preservation as an active ongoing choice rather than simply “taking no specific action”.

Two respondents additionally commented that, for them, the concept of an initial preservation period does not apply. These were, as entered:

“We have not recognized permanent preservation of records to have defined separate "initial" and "later" stages in the archives from the preservation point of view.”

and the coding example supplied above:

“We preserve data indefinitely or until the responsible organization asks for it to be deleted or returned to them. There is no ‘initial period’.”

Appraisal of existing holdings emerges in several comments as a key activity which attempts to balance the archival value, the value for future research and the historical record, and the resources available for preservation. Some respondents are clear that all data must be kept indefinitely (unless the initiating organisation asks for them to be deleted or returned), in order to maintain the scholarly record. Other organisations indicate willingness to dispose of data which have been infrequently accessed and/or are of unclear provenance. Only one organisation reported a policy of deletion at the end of the initial preservation period, unless specifically countermanded by the depositor.

5.3.7 Survey section 3: reflections

Answers in survey section 3 demonstrate a wide range of practices and types of interactivity with preserved digital objects as well as an interesting variety of organisational practices and policies, and a range of conceptual approaches to questions such as an "initial preservation period".

Among those respondents who did not answer question 3.4 on the length of the initial preservation commitment, there is a noticeably high frequency of the responses "I don't know", "we take no specific action" and lack of reply to question 3.5 on what happens to digital objects after the initial preservation period. This is perhaps one way of identifying respondents who are not familiar with their organisational commitment to length of initial preservation and subsequent handling of deposited objects, or alternatively, who are working for organisations without a clear policy or plan for these issues. Further investigation would be necessary here, on an individual basis, to ascertain the correct explanation.

5.4 Survey section 4: Discipline-specific requirements for long term preservation of digital objects

Questions in survey section 4 unpack some discipline-specific aspects of data preservation, including which descriptive metadata standards are commonly used in the organisation; whether the organisation recommends preferred file formats; arrangements around sensitive data or data that require specific protection for other reasons; and whether the designated community has needs that are currently unmet.

In survey section 4 we also asked about the concept of FAIR data but without using the acronym. We asked about factors that might reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of the digital data objects that are preserved by the organisation.

Some of these questions are open-ended and potentially complex but were designed to provoke reflection and hopefully elicit thoughtful, discursive responses from participants. All survey section 4 questions were written by WP3 colleagues³⁴ in collaboration with the WP1 team.

5.4.1 The descriptive metadata standards commonly used in the organisation

Colleagues from EDEN WP3 provided a list of "descriptive metadata standards" for respondents to consider and to indicate by tick box whether these are in use at their organisation (see Figure 49). Respondents could choose as many as were applicable, and 17 did not respond.

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15789261>. D3.1 contains a more detailed presentation of the discipline-specific questions.

Which descriptive metadata standard(s) is/are commonly used in your organisation?

- CMDI (Component MetaData Infrastructure)
- CRMtex
- DDI-C Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook
- DDI-L Data Documentation Initiative - Lifecycle
- DDI-CDI (Cross-Domain Integration)
- Dublin Core
- DataCite Metadata Schema
- DCAT
- Darwin Core/EML
- EAD (Encoded Archive Description)
- ENA (European Nucleotide Archive) metadata model/EGA model (life sciences)
- ISO 639-3 (Codes for the representation of names of languages – Part 3: Alpha-3 code for comprehensive coverage of languages)
- ISO19115 (Geographic information – Metadata)
- IMDI (ISLE MetaData Initiative)
- LIFT (Lexington Interchange Format)
- MARC
- MIAME/MINSEQ (life sciences)
- OLAC Metadata
- TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) Guidelines
- TEI/EPIDOC
- UMM (Unified Metadata Model)
- Other (please specify)

Figure 49: List of ‘descriptive metadata standards’ generated by WP3 colleagues.

Figure 50: Number of standards used per organisation (x axis=number of standards; y axis = number of responses).

We looked at the number of standards from this list used per organisation (see Figure 50). The largest category of respondents to this question (about 25%) reported using only 1 standard from the list provided, followed closely by those employing 2 or 3 standards per organisation (around 20% each). Thus, most responding organisations use between one and three descriptive standards in total (approximately 66%).

Figure 51: Descriptive metadata standards used, ranked from most to least frequently used. 13 out of 23 responses included.

The most frequently used descriptive standard (see Figure 51) is Dublin Core, adopted by about 63% of the respondents. EAD and DataCite are also widely applied, each being used by slightly more than 33% of the respondents.

It is worth mentioning that 8% of the responses were blank or invalid. Responses were considered invalid if the respondent selected ‘Other’ but did not indicate which standard. Perhaps these non-responses indicate a lack of clarity or awareness regarding the precise meaning of the term “descriptive standard”. Most of the standards that we suggested pertain to encoding or application standards rather than to conceptual models (e.g. EAD vs RiC or ISAD(G)). Many respondents suggested conceptual models rather than encoding standards. Moreover, some standards listed under the category “Other” do not qualify as descriptive standards (e.g. PREMIS). There may be more work to do to understand the difference perceived between descriptive and conceptual standards.

5.4.2 Whether the organisation recommends (a list of) preferred file formats

All respondents were asked whether their organisation recommends a list of preferred file formats with a “yes”, “no” or “I don’t know” answering choice. Response frequencies are shown in Figure 52, below.

Figure 52: Existence of (a list of) preferred file formats.

If the answer was “yes”, respondents were then asked (question 4.2A) to supply a link to the list if this is public, or otherwise to list the preferred formats in the text field.

A majority (n=148 of 250) of respondents reported that their organisation did recommend a list of preferred file formats, and of those, 109 elaborated as follows: 69 provided a URL, 20 shared a typed list of formats, 5 responses clarified that the list of formats is not public, and the remainder responded with discussion. We have not analysed the content of those recommended file format lists provided as URLs, within the scope of this survey analysis.

If the answer was “no”, i.e., the organisation does *not* have a list of preferred formats (n=79 of 250), then the respondent was asked (question 4.2B) to, instead, list the most common formats preserved by the organisation. Responses are indicated in Figure 53 below. This figure shows the percentage of those who reported the current use of a particular file format at their organisation, whether this answer was given as a textual suggestion (not a URL) in their response to question 4.2A (“If yes, please supply link to the list where this is public”) and/or their textual response to question 4.2B (“If no, please list the most common formats stored in the repository.”)

Figure 53: Response rate to the subsidiary, 'if no' question attached to question 4.2 "Does your organisation recommend (a list of) preferred file formats?" This question, Q4.2B, "Please list the most common formats stored in your repository", only appeared to the 79 participants who chose "no" to Q4.2.

As we can see in Figure 53, almost a third ($n=22$; 28% of 79 participants) of those indicating that they do not have a list of preferred file formats, did not respond to this follow-up question. This might be due to the sheer breadth of format options in use in contemporary digital preservation practice, as multiple respondents explained in the open text comments. For example, one respondent wrote: "So many different ones, varies a lot."

Those 57 participants who did respond to question 4.2B applied different strategies to answer this open text question. One strategy was describing the wider organisational or technical environment in which the organisation operates. The remainder of the 57 respondents chose to provide lists of their most common file formats (as intended by the survey designers). They all used file extensions to describe their most common formats.

This open-text question received reports of 45 different file formats. The 14 most popular file formats named by our respondents can be seen in Figure 54. The remaining formats received less than 5 reports.

Figure 54: Most frequently-reported file formats held by respondents' organisations.

Among the 57 respondents filling out the open question regarding their most common file formats, 71% mentioned PDF. This is clearly the most frequently reported file format and the only one occurring in more than 50% of responses.

A different view on these results is provided by Figure 55, where we have grouped the results by file type. The detailed breakdown of this grouping is available in Table 23, [Appendix B](#).

Figure 55: All reported file formats classified by file type.

As mentioned above, we have not yet analysed the given recommended file format lists further within the scope of this survey analysis. For future work in the project, it may prove worthwhile to extract the information from the list of file formats (Figure 54) and add them to other related analysis by WP1, 2 and 3 to have a more complete picture.

We also found it noteworthy that the amount of discipline-specific file formats is comparatively low. In future work, a breakdown of the file formats reported above analysed by organisation class would be helpful. As is, the figure could lead to the argument that PDF is highly reported because there are so many archives and libraries amongst our respondents, but we caution against this assumption as it may be a file format listed very often by non-GLAM organisations as well.

5.4.3 Whether the organisation accepts sensitive data/data that requires specific protection

In this question, we asked whether the respondent’s organisation accepts sensitive data or data that requires specific protection for any other reason. Response options were ‘yes’, ‘no’, and ‘I don’t know’. This question attracted a healthy response rate with only 1.2% choosing to not answer. Results are shown in Figure 56.

Figure 56: Acceptance of sensitive/protected data.

Approximately two thirds of respondents (n=153, 61.2%) indicated that their organisation accepts sensitive data/data that requires protection. Within this group, 150 respondents provided more detailed information regarding the types of sensitive data they accept, and 100 respondents reported more detailed information on the protection measures they implement.

As discussed above in Section 2, we used the list of data protection reasons provided in the UNESCO Recommendation On Open Science³⁵. For each category of sensitive/protected data identified as relevant, the respondent was invited to specify the types of protection measure(s) taken by their organisation. This list was only shown to respondents who answered 'yes' to question 4.3 and the types of protection that the respondent could choose from are shown in Figure 57.

³⁵ <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMF8546>, pp. 11-12.

Does your organisation accept sensitive data, or data that requires specific protection?

Yes
 No
 I don't know.

Please specify the reason(s) why protection is required by your data objects:

Protection of human rights
 Protection of national security
 Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study
 Protection of legal process and public order
 Protection of intellectual property rights
 Protection of personal information
 Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge
 Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species
 Other (please specify)

Figure 57: Choice of reasons for protection of data objects.

The 153 respondents who reported that they did accept sensitive data further clarified the reasons for protection as set out in Figure 58, and Table 24 (Appendix B), from most to least frequent.

Figure 58: Reasons for protection of data objects.

The responses supplied as “other” (n=9)—with proposed mapping to the existing categories where applicable, in square brackets—were (shown here exactly as entered):

- We preserve data related to nationally important cultural heritage and art.
- The Act on the Openness of Government Activities specifies records that are secret. [*Legal process, possibly National security*]
- On conditions specified by legal agreements with business sector partners, but only if it is classified as confidential not data subjected to strict secrecy according to internal classification system.
- For a list of grounds for restricting access, see (link).
- detailed address [*Personal information*]
- Data with specific coordinates that could lead to looting if published.
- data from private sector is provided under these restrictions.
- clinical trial data that is both confidential and needs to be protected to ensure health and safety of study participants.
- animal rights.

We can see at least two of these responses appear to relate to important and potentially vulnerable art or other cultural heritage objects – this is comparable to the condition, "Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species" but for cultural heritage artefacts rather than plants or animals. The other theme that emerges here is that of data holdings subject to business/private sector interests, which again arises in two responses. We may or may not be able to map these accurately to the answer option, "Protection of intellectual property rights"; it is not possible to say with this paucity of information (but this could be an interesting area to investigate further in interviews).

We also invited respondents to use a free text field to specify the protection measures for each type of sensitivity chosen. Responses here provide a small range of expected measures such as access restrictions of various kinds; encryption; anonymisation and pseudo-anonymisation; and user authentication methods. The full set of responses is provided in Table 25, [Appendix B](#).

5.4.4 Whether the designated community has needs that the organisation does not currently address

We asked respondents, "Does your designated community have needs that your organisation does not currently address?" Response options were 'yes', 'no', or 'I don't know'. Initial responses are shown in Figure 59 below.

This question was deliberately designed to offer an opportunity for reflection: firstly on the notion of "designated community", and then also on the extent to which the organisation is meeting those community needs.

Figure 59: Current perceived provision of needs of designated community.

This question enjoyed a high response rate, with only 1.2% survey participants failing to respond to it. However, this question appears to have been formulated in a manner that either introduced “designated community” as an unfamiliar term, and/or took respondents into unfamiliar territory in other ways, as a substantial minority of respondents (40.5% overall) selected “I don’t know.”

In Figure 60, we show responses by organisation class. There seems to be a lot of uncertainty in all organisation classes around the knowledge and implementation of the notion of designated community (see “I don’t know” responses) including, surprisingly, archives. This reminds us that not all archives staff members are necessarily familiar with the OAIS reference model (of which “designated community” is a key concept³⁶). Alternatively, the high rate of “I don’t know” responses here may have nothing to do with the understanding of the concept of “designated community”; rather, it may be that these respondents are simply not involved in understanding community needs.

However, it also seems that the designated community is a concept that “Research infrastructure” and “Repository” respondents are currently occupied with, as almost a third of both org classes indicated awareness of unaddressed needs in their respective communities.

³⁶ <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/dpc-technology-watch-publications/technology-watch-guidance-notes/2856-designated-community-guidance-note/file>

Figure 60: Perceptions of unmet designated community needs, categorised by org class.

Out of those 94 respondents who answered “yes”, 77 respondents (i.e. 81.9% of those who answered yes) provided open text information on the needs of their designated community which the respondent believes are currently not met. These responses were coded to 28 themes (see [Appendix C](#)).

The most common concerns that emerged from this question were issues around:

- sensitive data and/or the protection of data holdings;
- dealing with large data volumes that are either currently or imminently being ingested;
- developing online access provision to meet current or imminent user needs.

Other concerns that were less frequently reported - but still voiced by several participants - were around:

- a lack of long-term provision of service;
- a lack of necessary policy or directives;
- ways to handle software preservation;
- provenance issues; and
- various format problems.

5.4.5 Factors that could reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of digital data objects preserved by the organisation

We asked respondents whether, in their opinion, there were factors that could reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of digital data objects preserved by their organisation. They were offered a free-text box in which to enter their response.

With this question, we aimed to bring digital preservation practitioners into direct dialogue with the notion of FAIR data; specifically, the notion of FAIR over time. As with the previous question, this

was deliberately designed to be a very open discussion-starter—as much to get practitioners reflecting on these issues as for us to gather data from them. Altogether, 171 respondents supplied a textual response, and these were coded to 60 themes (see [Appendix C](#)). Of these, 12 themes occurred 10 or more times. These are shown here in table 26, in order of decreasing frequency.

Table 26: Factors that could reduce FAIR over time, in order of decreasing frequency: all options with 10 or more responses.

Factor	Number of mentions
Budget/finance issues	43
Metadata/documentation: missing	42
Metadata/documentation: insufficient quality	24
Technology change/obsolescence	20
Staffing: insufficient numbers	19
Formats: changing/obsolescence	19
Access issues	15
Software issues	13
Political/legislative threats	13
Data volume/file sizes	10
Insufficient appraisal/migration/checking	10
Formats: proprietary	10

Whilst these are not identical to the responses to the previous question 4.4 (around the needs of the designated community), we see some recurrence of themes. When this list was presented at International Data Week 2025³⁷, there were certainly no expressions of surprise to hear that budget/finance issues and quantity or quality of metadata were at the top of the list. We intend to perform further analysis of the qualitative data gathered in response to these two latter questions (about on unmet community needs and about threats to FAIR over time) in relation to organisational class, and we anticipate that WP3 colleagues will be interested in examining the data gathered from these two questions through a discipline-specific lens.

5.4.6 Survey section 4: reflections

The themes emerging from the responses regarding threats to FAIR over time (Q4.5) were generated independently of the analysis of the responses to the earlier question about needs of the designated community (Q4.4).

³⁷ <https://scidatacon.org/event/9/contributions/74/>

However, it is worth noting that several of the themes reoccur in responses to both of these questions. The three most common themes arising from the designated community question were:

- sensitive/protected data;
- data volume; and
- issues around access provision.

We see here that two of these - data volume and access issues - recur in the top answers around threats to FAIR over time.

Sensitive data issues were flagged in 3 responses, and the other issues reported in Q4.4—long-term provision of service; lack of useful policy/directive; software preservation; provenance issues and various format problems—also all recur at low rates in the responses to Q4.5. This is not particularly surprising—these are clearly frequently experienced challenges in the practice of preservation—but it is interesting to see that they are considered by respondents both from the perspective of directly meeting the needs of the community i.e. user-centred approaches, and also the arguably more theoretical perspective introduced when considering keeping digital data objects FAIR. As mentioned above, we intend to analyse this qualitative data further in relation to organisation class; this may identify interesting outliers for interview purposes.

6 Lessons learned and next steps

In this section we reflect briefly on various aspects of the work described in this report, including the process of creating and running this research; key findings; possible lessons learned; and next steps for this strand of work, both within and outwith WP1.

6.1 Reflections on the survey process

We made a decision early on to make the survey as flexible as possible for respondents, specifically by not making any of the questions mandatory. The downside of this approach was that some records³⁸, while partially useful, are missing responses to some of the questions; the upside is that this flexibility encouraged a notably large number of completed surveys, including the submission of responses from participants who might otherwise have not submitted their overall response to the survey due to the time requirement, or who prefer to review all the questions in advance before participating. In addition, we are pleased to have received so many responses from the international community and to have managed to elicit responses from digital preservation practitioners from a range of organisation types and sizes.

Inevitably there were questions from respondents about how to answer descriptive data points, such as organisation type or size; most commonly how to consider one's organisation at the overall organisational level or in terms of one's unit (for example, a digital preservation unit within a national library). Ultimately, we wanted respondents to be able to self-define as far as possible and so we left respondents to choose the level at which they wish to describe their organisation, but this led to some uncertainty from respondents about how to complete this section.

Due to the disproportionate number of responses from Europe, the low number of responses from many other global regions and the lack of responses from Africa and the Middle East, the data should not be seen as a reflection of global practice. Rather, we have a reasonable overview of some aspects of European and North American practice, and the beginnings of an understanding

³⁸ i.e the set of answers supplied by a single participant.

of practice in Australasia. It is clear, however, that to better understand practice in Asia and across the global south including central and southern America and Africa, we need to better understand how to reach colleagues in these regions, how to support and encourage dialogue, and how to better tailor our research activities in order to make the case for their participation.

Another improvement that would have provided helpful insight would have been a different approach to organisational size. Free-text responses indicated that some respondents found it difficult to accurately reflect their working context as, for example, they may be officially located within a large organisation but be working in a small digital preservation team or department. We asked the organisational size question in order to gain a brief idea of the context for each respondent but on reflection we would have gained more useful information had we asked directly about the size of the team and/or budget for digital preservation activity in their current professional context. This would have been likely to deter some from responding, but may have enhanced clarity for those that did respond.

6.2 Reflections on key findings

The overarching aim of the research activity described in this report was to dig into the practices current in digital preservation, and the reference documents that are used to guide these practices, in order to better understand how the digital preservation community currently approaches identification, selection and appraisal practices when considering ‘long-term’ preservation of digital data objects. Some of the findings that we find noteworthy are as follows:

- The survey responses have the potential to enrich EDEN’s understanding of the 7 discipline-specific early adopter disciplines on which WP3 is focusing. These are derived from the 7 discipline areas (Climate Simulations, Earth and Environmental Sciences, Food Sciences, High-Energy Physics, Life Sciences and Bioinformatics, Linguistics, and Social Sciences) represented by repositories participating in the EDEN project. The survey takes discipline-specific and discipline-agnostic data preservation into consideration, to minimise risk of an unintentionally narrow discipline-specific focus.
- One of the most striking findings was the high proportion of respondents who are working at an organisation where there is no agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ in the digital preservation context. This means that one of the premises upon which we are working in WP1 - ‘long-term preservation’ - is actually far from being a stable concept. Even those respondents who did have an agreed or working definition of ‘long-term’ offered a wide range of numerical definitions of what that means for them and their preservation work.
- We note with interest the existing connections indicated by respondents, between the digital preservation realm and what is currently designated FAIR data. These connections appeared in two different places: first, the discussion introduced by respondents about the importance of maintaining findability and access, whatever the agreed preservation period; and second, the high level of awareness and use of the FAIR principles reported in the analysis of frameworks, standards and guidelines. This reminds us that many of the ideas now encapsulated in the FAIR principles have been, to some extent, bedrocks of preservation practice for years. There is, however, no similar visibility at this time of the TRUST³⁹ or CARE⁴⁰ principles within the responses from our participants.
- Some common themes emerged around needs of the designated community and threats to FAIR over time, notably: sensitive / protected data; data volume; and issues around access

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

⁴⁰ <https://www.gida-global.org/care>; <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-042>

provision. We see here that two of the top three designated community needs - data volume and access issues - recur in the top answers around threats to FAIR over time. Sensitive data issues were flagged in 3 responses, and the other designated community needs—long-term provision of service; lack of useful policy/directive; software preservation; provenance issues and various format problems—also all recur at low rates in the threats to FAIR over time. This is not particularly surprising—these are clearly frequently experienced challenges in the practice of preservation—but it is interesting to see that they are considered by respondents both from the perspective of directly meeting the needs of the community i.e. user-centred approaches, and also the arguably more theoretical perspective introduced when considering keeping digital data objects FAIR. Ultimately, though, FAIR data are data that meet user needs. It is a useful piece of validation that these themes recur in the responses to these two questions.

6.3 Next steps

We gathered the following list of activities arising from the research described here, that we will consider within our WP work plan, or in associated activities.

6.3.1 Applications of results within EDEN WP1

Here, we indicate the selected findings that we consider most applicable to future activity in our work package.

- The interpretation of the net diagrams revealed that further in-depth analysis of the different types of quality checks is desirable. By converting the data into a relative representation, we hope to enhance the readability of the diagrams, and further investigate sectoral as well as organisational particularities.
- The net diagram analysis on technical checks is useful to T1.2 work on the Core Preservation Processes. Further analysis and cross-checks on the quality checks can be undertaken to support the metrics part of T1.2.
- How different org classes think of or work with the notion of designated community can feed usefully into the reappraisal framework work of T1.3, including consideration of how results inform us of reappraisal trends, and/or whether there is a need or appetite for awareness of risk of a lack of reappraisal.
- It will be useful to combine the relevant results of D3.1 and D1.1 for the enrichment of the Re-use Fitness Framework. From the survey, sections presented here (report section 5.3 in particular) inform the three quality pillars (technical data quality, contextual data quality, metadata quality). Particular attention should be paid to responses about which quality checks are currently used. By paying attention to this data, we can work towards better understanding good practice.
- The Re-use Fitness Framework element “Trustworthy digital archive capabilities” (i.e. one of the horizontal bars of the model) has been largely described in M1.1 Core Preservation Processes⁴¹. The approach to collecting the M1.1 CPP candidates was a qualitative rather than quantitative one - they were derived from existing guidelines and frameworks. The results from the survey allow us to:
 - Identify gaps for CPP adoption by organisation types and discipline;
 - Identify candidates to potentially supply more use cases and reference implementations of the CPPs, where respondents have indicated willingness for further contact;

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452>

D1.1 questions have strongest links to the following Core Preservation Processes from M1.1:

- CPP-008 File Format Identification
- CPP-009 Metadata Extraction
- CPP-010 File Format Validation
- CPP-016 Metadata Ingest and Management
- CPP-018 Community Watch
- CPP-019 Data Quality Assessment
- CPP-023 Risk Definition and Extraction
- CPP-026 File Normalization
- CPP-029 Ingest.

It will be helpful to apply a mapping of the survey questions to the CPPs.

- The second Re-use Fitness Framework horizontal element, “Preservation Objective/Designated Community Needs” is clearly relevant to question 4.4 on community needs, and to some degree also question 4.5 on threats to FAIR over time. The answers to those questions did suggest some possible trends. For Q4.4, the preservation objective and designated community needs frequently listed “large data volumes”, “sensitive data” and “online access for imminent user needs” - these trends should be explored further in combination with the different quality pillars of the model (e.g., what are the technical / contextual / metadata requirements for sensitive data) and usage scenarios as concrete preservation objectives (e.g., what are the methods in which we expect our users to interact with that data, such as anonymised / non-anonymised). Concrete use cases for this should be extracted from the disciplines represented in the project (i.e., by identifying repositories represented in the EDEN project that represent each use case - if there are none, by finding one from D3.1 and D1.1 respondents that opted to be available for further contact) and requirements be explored using their concrete use cases. The criteria for the re-use fitness framework can be extracted from these specific use cases in a first step and be compared against other use cases following the same methodology.

6.3.2 Contributions to / connections with other EDEN WPs

Here, we indicate the selected findings that we consider most applicable to future activity in other EOSC EDEN work packages.

- Survey results can usefully feed into WP2 tools and service development and WP3 user journey maps.
- We can crosscheck results with findings of D3.1 - Report on Discipline Requirements and Needs; while T3.1 supplied some questions for the survey, the T3.1 team also conducted desk-based mapping and standalone interviews to identify discipline specific requirements: it may be interesting to understand whether there is a difference between the discipline-specific requirements identified in D3.1 and the key findings of this survey. The file formats in particular (but also other practices we investigated) can be compared to the results gathered by WP3 in their interview/landscape deliverable, as well as any touchpoints in the survey work performed by our sister project FIDELIS.
- The survey data will help WP3 identify and select aspects to focus on in their continuous work on identifying requirements and needs.

6.3.3 Potential further correlations or connections to investigate with the survey data

Here, we indicate some potential correlations or connections that we consider most amenable to future investigation.

- There are various potential correlations between, for example, certain organisation classes and certain decisions or behaviours that may offer potential for future research. For example, the 'Archives' acquisition strategy looks distinct from that of other org classes. The organisation type 'Museum or gallery' stands out by exhibiting low values for quality checking. There may be useful further analysis of file formats by org type or by org class to identify any potential patterns. We are also interested in analysing the reported threats to FAIR by organisation type.
- Regarding the possible impact the intended preservation time has on quality checks, it may be of interest to know whether institutions who want to preserve longer conduct more quality checks at the point of entry.
- Where there was an existing definition of 'long term', we asked to see the text if it was publicly available and we also asked specifically on what the definition was based. Further analysis of these sources could be useful. For example, for national libraries and archives, this definition is often legal deposit / archival law-based, whereas for repositories it is often an organisational mandate. This may be another marker of differences between organisational types or classes.

6.4 Summary

This report has presented the context, aims, methodology and results from the first data collection by WP1 of the EOSC EDEN project. Data have been collected from 250 digital preservation practitioners from a range of organisation types around the world, with a particular concentration of respondents from western Europe. Key practices, definitions and resources currently in use in contemporary digital preservation practice are presented and future relevant routes for investigation are suggested. Suggestions are made of where these findings may best be deployed by this and other EOSC EDEN work packages.

7 References

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Appendix A: Survey question set

The complete set of survey questions is available to view and download at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15528660>

This document provides the text and answering options for both the ‘top-line’ questions (i.e. those asked to every participant) and the subsidiary questions.

Appendix B: Tables

Table 2: Organisation locations.

Please choose from this list of UN member states. Select 'Other' if your state/country does not appear:	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 250)
Germany	66	26.4%
United States of America	29	11.6%
United Kingdom	14	5.6%
France	13	5.2%
Canada	11	4.4%
Finland	11	4.4%
Sweden	11	4.4%
Australia	10	4.0%
Switzerland	10	4.0%
Austria	8	3.2%
Belgium	8	3.2%
Croatia	7	2.8%
Netherlands	7	2.8%
Norway	7	2.8%
China	4	1.6%
New Zealand	4	1.6%
Poland	4	1.6%
India	3	1.2%
Ireland	3	1.2%
Portugal	3	1.2%
Brazil	2	0.8%
Denmark	2	0.8%

Italy	2	0.8%
Luxembourg	2	0.8%
Iceland	1	0.4%
Israel	1	0.4%
Latvia	1	0.4%
Lithuania	1	0.4%
Mongolia	1	0.4%
Slovenia	1	0.4%
Spain	1	0.4%
Other	1	0.4%
No Answer	1	0.4%

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Table 3: Organisation size results.

The size of your organisation is:	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Micro (<10 full-time employees or equivalent).	30	12.00%
Small (11-50 full time employees or equivalent).	48	19.20%
Medium (51-250 full time employees or equivalent).	76	30.40%
Large (251+ full time employees or equivalent).	94	37.60%
No Answer	2	0.80%

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Table 4: Organisational role type results.

Your own role within the organisation is:	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Practitioner (digital archivist, preservation specialist, research data manager, digital curator, data steward, data librarian, etc.)	165	66.00%
Middle management (team manager, section manager, programme manager, etc.)	77	30.80%

Senior management (senior manager, senior administrator, executive director, CTO, etc.)	30	12.00%
No Answer	1	0.40%

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Table 6: Guidelines and frameworks (all responses) ranked by frequency of use.

Institutional preservation policy	<i>n</i>	Ratio
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Heard of, and currently use	155	62.00%
Heard of but do not currently use	43	17.20%
Have not heard of	39	15.60%
No Answer	13	5.20%
Collection development policy/statement/strategy	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	141	56.40%
Heard of but do not currently use	42	16.80%
Have not heard of	58	23.20%
No Answer	9	3.60%
ISO 14721 OAIS reference model	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	136	54.40%
Heard of but do not currently use	71	28.40%
Have not heard of	40	16.00%
No Answer	3	1.20%
The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	130	52.00%
Heard of but do not currently use	64	25.60%
Have not heard of	51	20.40%
No Answer	5	2.00%
PREMIS	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	82	32.80%
Heard of but do not currently use	98	39.20%

Have not heard of	58	23.20%
No Answer	12	4.80%
CoreTrustSeal certification	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	63	25.20%
Heard of but do not currently use	120	48.00%
Have not heard of	63	25.20%
No Answer	4	1.60%
ISO 15489 Information and documentation -- Records management	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	52	20.80%
Heard of but do not currently use	89	35.60%
Have not heard of	101	40.40%
No Answer	8	3.20%
ISO/IEC 27001 Information technology -- Security techniques -- Information security management systems	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	44	17.60%
Heard of but do not currently use	80	32.00%
Have not heard of	119	47.60%
No Answer	7	2.80%
ISO 19005 Electronic document file format for long-term preservation	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	39	15.60%
Heard of but do not currently use	103	41.20%
Have not heard of	100	40.00%

No Answer	8	3.20%
Unlisted: Other framework or guideline	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	39	15.60%
Heard of but do not currently use	11	4.40%
Have not heard of	76	30.40%
No Answer	124	49.60%
DIN 31644 Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	34	13.60%
Heard of but do not currently use	108	43.20%
Have not heard of	103	41.20%
No Answer	5	2.00%
ISO 16363 Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	27	10.80%
Heard of but do not currently use	128	51.20%
Have not heard of	89	35.60%
No Answer	6	2.40%
ISO 18492 Long-term preservation of electronic document-based information	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	21	8.40%
Heard of but do not currently use	119	47.60%
Have not heard of	103	41.20%
No Answer	7	2.80%

NDSA Digital Curation Decision Guide	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	21	8.40%
Heard of but do not currently use	67	26.80%
Have not heard of	153	61.20%
No Answer	9	3.60%
EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation - Recommendations and assertions	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	15	6.00%
Heard of but do not currently use	89	35.60%
Have not heard of	134	53.60%
No Answer	12	4.80%
CCSDS 653.0-M-1: Information Preparation to enable Long-Term Use	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Heard of, and currently use	11	4.40%
Heard of but do not currently use	62	24.80%
Have not heard of	166	66.40%
No Answer	11	4.40%

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Table 7: Guidelines and frameworks ranked by frequency of use.

Response: Heard of, and currently use	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Institutional preservation policy	155	62.0%
Collection development policy/statement/strategy	141	56.4%
ISO 14721 OAIS reference model	136	54.4%
The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship	130	52.0%
PREMIS	82	32.8%
CoreTrustSeal certification	63	25.2%
ISO 15489 Information and documentation -- Records management	52	20.8%
ISO/IEC 27001 Information technology -- Security techniques -- Information security management systems	44	17.6%
ISO 19005 Electronic document file format for long-term preservation	39	15.6%
DIN 31644 Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives	34	13.6%
ISO 16363 Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories	27	10.8%
ISO 18492 Long-term preservation of electronic document-based information	21	8.4%
NDSA Digital Curation Decision Guide	21	8.4%
EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation - Recommendations and assertions	15	6.0%
CCSDS 653.0-M-1: Information Preparation to enable Long-Term Use	11	4.4%

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Table 8: Guidelines and frameworks ranked by response “Heard of, but do not currently use”.

Response: Heard of, but do not currently use	n	Ratio
ISO 16363 Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories	128	51.2%
CoreTrustSeal certification	120	48.0%
ISO 18492 Long-term preservation of electronic document-based information	119	47.6%
DIN 31644 Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives	108	43.2%
ISO 19005 Electronic document file format for long-term preservation	103	41.2%
PREMIS	98	39.2%
EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation - Recommendations and assertions	89	35.6%
ISO 15489 Information and documentation -- Records management	89	35.6%
ISO/IEC 27001 Information technology -- Security techniques -- Information security management systems	80	32.0%
ISO 14721 OAIS reference model	71	28.4%
NDSA Digital Curation Decision Guide	67	26.8%
The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship	64	25.6%
CCSDS 653.0-M-1: Information Preparation to enable Long-Term Use	62	24.8%
Institutional preservation policy	43	17.2%
Collection development policy/statement/strategy	42	16.8%

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Table 9: Guidelines and frameworks ranked by response “Have not heard of”.

Response: Have not heard of	n	Ratio
CCSDS 653.0-M-1: Information Preparation to enable Long-Term Use	166	66.4%
NDSA Digital Curation Decision Guide	153	61.2%

EOSC Task Force on Long Term Data Preservation - Recommendations and assertions	134	53.6%
ISO/IEC 27001 Information technology -- Security techniques -- Information security management systems	119	47.6%
ISO 18492 Long-term preservation of electronic document-based information	103	41.2%
DIN 31644 Information and documentation - Criteria for trustworthy digital archives	103	41.2%
ISO 15489 Information and documentation -- Records management	101	40.4%
ISO 19005 Electronic document file format for long-term preservation	100	40.0%
ISO 16363 Audit and certification of trustworthy digital repositories	89	35.6%
CoreTrustSeal certification	63	25.2%
Collection development policy/statement/strategy	58	23.2%
PREMIS	58	23.2%
The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship	51	20.4%
ISO 14721 OAIS reference model	40	16.0%
Institutional preservation policy	39	15.6%

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Table 10: Existence of agreed or working definition of "long term".

In your organisation, do you have an agreed or working definition of "long-term" in the context of digital preservation?	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Yes	130	51.8%
No	112	44.8%
No Answer	8	3.2%

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Table 11: Reasons for lack of agreed or working definition of "long term". Respondents were able to choose more than one answer; figures here are analysed without the use of the "Multiple reasons" category.

Is there a specific reason that you don't currently have an agreed or working definition of "long-term" in the context of digital preservation?	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 112 responses)	Ratio (of 250 responses)
We have not yet achieved consensus on a definition.	41	36.6%	16.4%
A definition is planned or in progress.	36	32.1%	14.4%
Other reason.	35	31.3%	14.0%
We don't need one as we do not do "long-term" preservation.	7	6.25%	2.8%

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Table 13: How digital data objects usually enter the organisation. Responses listed by most to least frequent.

How do digital data objects for preservation usually enter your organisation? Please select as many responses as appropriate.	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Self-deposit by researcher on a voluntary basis.	157	62.80%
Funder-mandated deposit by researcher (e.g. policy-driven; funding agency requirements).	119	47.60%
Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring: depositors are identified and invited to submit their data.	111	44.40%
Parent-organisation deposit (e.g. repository is part of a research institution).	90	36.00%
Deposit as a result of proactive monitoring: harvesting of data objects.	67	26.80%
Third party data preservation collaboration (e.g. preservation-as-a-service).	63	25.20%
Other - please specify.	55	22.00%
I don't know.	5	2.00%
No Answer	1	0.40%

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Table 14: Whether data objects are assessed for quality at point of ingest.

Do you assess the quality of digital data objects at the point of ingest for "long-term" preservation? Please select as many responses as appropriate.	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 250)
---	-----------------	-----------------------

Yes for the quality of descriptive metadata (e.g. creator, subject, description, research theme).	174	69.6%
Yes for the quality of administrative metadata (e.g. rights, licenses, access conditions).	170	68.0%
Yes for technical quality of the data (e.g. correct rendering, conforming to standard specifications).	161	64.4%
Yes for the quality of technical metadata (e.g. format, resolution, MD5 checksum).	159	63.6%
Yes for content/information quality of the data (e.g. authenticity, uniqueness, reliability, completeness).	144	57.6%
No.	28	11.2%
I don't know.	8	3.2%
No Answer	2	0.8%

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Table 15: Assessments of technical quality of data objects performed at point of ingest.

Which assessments do you undertake to assess the technical quality of the data?	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 161)	Ratio (of 250)
File format identification	150	93.2%	60.0%
Integrity checking	136	84.5%	54.4%
File format validation	125	77.6%	50.0%
Opening data with software / visual inspection	118	73.3%	47.2%
Virus checking	113	70.2%	45.2%
Normalisation / migration	90	55.9%	36.0%
No Answer	89	55.3%	35.6%
Other	6	3.7%	2.4%

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Table 16: Assessments of content/information quality of data objects performed at point of ingest.

Which assessments do you undertake to assess the content/information quality of the data?	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 250)
No Answer	107	42.8%
Provenance	103	41.2%
Completeness	101	40.4%
Level of documentation	91	36.4%
Originality	70	28.0%
Compliance with scientific best-practices	44	17.6%
Reproducibility	42	16.8%
Other (please specify).	11	4.4%

[Back to Section 5.3.2.2.](#)

Table 17: Occurrence of regular reassessment of quality of preserved digital data objects.

Do you regularly re-assess the quality of your preserved digital data objects?	<i>n</i>	Ratio (of 250)
No.	144	57.60%
Yes.	69	27.60%
I don't know.	33	13.20%
No Answer	4	1.60%

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Table 23: Classification of file format input into file format types.

Input	Wikidata label	QID	File Format Wiki page ID	Library of Congress Format Description Document ID	PRONOM file format ID	formatType
TAR	tar	Q283579	Tape_Archive	fdd000531	x-fmt/265	Aggregate
WARC	Web ARChive	Q7978505	WARC	fdd000236	fmt/289	Aggregate
ZIP	ZIP	Q136218	ZIP	fdd000354	x-fmt/263	Aggregate
MP3	MP3	Q42591	MP3	fdd000012	fmt/134	Audio
MP4	MPEG-4 Part 14	Q336316	MP4	fdd000037	fmt/199	Audio
WAV	Waveform Audio File Format	Q217570	WAV	fdd000001	fmt/6	Audio
AVI	Audio Video Interleave	Q209054	AVI	fdd000059	fmt/5	Audio
FLAC	Free Lossless Audio Codec	Q131481410	FLAC	fdd000198	fmt/279	Audio
MPEG-4	MPEG-4	Q219763	MP4, MPEG-4	fdd000037	fmt/199	Audio
CSV	comma-separated values	Q935809	CSV	fdd000323	x-fmt/18	Dataset
hDf5	HDF5	Q61080677		fdd000440		Dataset
Parquet	Apache Parquet	Q28915683		fdd000575	fmt/2023	Dataset

Sav(spss)	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences data file	Q28848214	SAV		fmt/638	Dataset
SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences output file	Q29943954			fmt/274	Dataset
TAB	tab-separated values	Q3513566	Tab_delimited	fdd000533	x-fmt/13	Dataset
tsv	tab-separated values	Q3513566	Tab_delimited	fdd000533	x-fmt/13	Dataset
mat	MAT-file	Q28770627	MAT			Dataset
SHP	shapefile	Q278934	Shapefile	fdd000280	x-fmt/235	GIS
HTML	HyperText Markup Language	Q62626012	HTML	fdd000475	fmt/96	Mark-up Text
XML	XML	Q2115	XML	fdd000075, fdd000263	fmt/101	Mark-up Text
PDF	PDF	Q42332	PDF	fdd000030	[multiple]	Page Description
PST	Personal Folder File	Q29651120	Personal_Folder_File	fdd000378, fdd000377	X-fmt/248, x-fmt/249	Personal data
TXT	text file	Q86920	Plain_text		x-fmt/111	Plain text
PPTX	Office Open XML Presentation Document, Strict, ISO/IEC 29500:2008	Q26207727	PPTX	fdd000395	fmt/1829	Presentation
JS	JavaScript format	Q5924007	JavaScript		x-fmt/423	Programming language

PY	Python	Q28865				Programming language
JPEG	JPEG	Q2195	JPEG	fdd000017	fmt/41 et al.	Raster Image
TIFF	TIFF	Q215106	TIFF	fdd000022 et al.	fmt/353	Raster Image
JP2	JPEG 2000	Q931783	JPEG_2000	fdd000143	x-fmt/392, fmt/463	Raster Image
GIF	GIF	Q2192	GIF	fdd000133	fmt/3,fmt/4	Raster Image or Video
XLSX	Office Open XML Spreadsheet Document, Strict, ISO/IEC 29500:2008	Q26207712	XLSX	fdd000401	fmt/1828	Spreadsheet
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets file format family	Q27826463	Cascading_Style_Sheets	fdd000482	x-fmt/224	Structured Text
epub	EPUB	Q475488	EPUB	fdd000310	fmt/483	Structured Text
mbox	Mbox	Q285972	Mbox	fdd000383	fmt/720	Structured Text
MOV	QuickTime File Format	Q942350	QuickTime	fdd000052	x-fmt/384	Video
DPX	Digital Picture Exchange, version 1	Q27967437	DPX	fdd000178	fmt/193	Video
FFV1/MKV	FFV1	Q579857		fdd000341		Video
MKV	Matroska	Q223535	Matroska	fdd000342	fmt/569	Video

MXF	Material Exchange Format	Q1893311	MXF	fdd000013	fmt/200, fmt/783, fmt/784, fmt/785, fmt/786, fmt/787, fmt/788, fmt/789, fmt/790, fmt/791	Video
mxm	Material Exchange Format	Q1893311	MXF	fdd000013	fmt/200, fmt/783, fmt/784, fmt/785, fmt/786, fmt/787, fmt/788, fmt/789, fmt/790, fmt/791	Video
MOV	QuickTime File Format	Q942350	QuickTime	fdd000052	x-fmt/384	Video
MPEG-2	MPEG-2 program stream	Q28018471	MPEG-2	fdd000637	x-fmt/386	Video
DOCX	Office Open XML Wordprocessing Document, Strict, ISO/IEC 29500:2008	Q26207675	DOCX	fdd000400	fmt/1827	Word Processor
dat	DAT	Q32097740				Unknown
jasp	jasp					Unknown

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Table 24: Reasons for protection of data objects.

Please specify the reason(s) why protection is required by your data objects.	<i>n</i>	Ratio
Protection of personal information	137	54.80%
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study	115	46.00%
Protection of intellectual property rights	96	38.40%
Protection of legal process and public order	61	24.40%
Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge	47	18.80%
Protection of human rights	44	17.60%
Protection of national security	41	16.40%
Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species	17	6.80%
Other (please specify)	9	3.60%

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Table 25: Protection measures taken.

Responses are provided here exactly as entered, other than redactions which are presented in square brackets.

Reason(s) why protection is required	Other type(s) of sensitive data, and protection measure(s) taken	For each type of sensitivity chosen, protection measure(s) taken
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Other (please specify)	clinical trial data that is both confidential and needs to be protected to ensure health and safety of study participants.	(a) security measures to ensure confidentiality and controlled access, (b) digital preservation to meet GxP Data Integrity ALCOA+ principles.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		A "prepare your data" checklist has a section on data privacy and the steps to be taken [link]. The review process double-checks the compliance
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Access denied except for ...
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Access conditions are applied
Protection of personal information		Access control
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information		access control, prior agreement by the data producer
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		access is restricted to specific users only
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Access restrictions to external users and access restrictions internally.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Access restriction periods according to regional legal frameworks
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for		Access restrictions and secure storage

human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Access restrictions, many records are closed to public/those outside the Archives and require special permission to access.
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Access to objects can be limited to bona fide researchers who must apply directly to collection managers (depositors, data owners) for access, which is time limited to a year by default.
Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Access to the archive database is restricted
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		According to data classification and [link].
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		All is off grid in three different locations and formats. 2x usb drives and one tape
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		All of the chosen boxes have mostly the same protection measures taken, and for security measures we cannot specify. Some have extra protection.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		all sensitive data is stored in a high secured storage system with restricted access. Data is only accessible if requested and after passing a confidentiality review. If data contains sensitive personal information an approved ethical review must be presented.

Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species;Other (please specify)	The Act on the Openness of Government Activities specifies records that are secret.	All sensitive information from government agencies is given the same protection by technical and administrative measures, e.g. access restrictions.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		all: access restrictions applied
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Anonymisation (only for dissemination), pseudonymisation (only for dissemination), user authentication, safe room
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		anonymisation, pseudonymisation, restricted access, terms and conditions of use
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		anonymisation/pseudonymisation
Protection of personal information;Other (please specify)	detailed address	anonymization
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Anonymization, Scientific Use Files, Secure Use Files
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Anonymization; closed access
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		As a rule, all archive material is protected as sensitive data by use restrictions and agreements.
Protection of personal information		as far as I know, we don't have that kind of document in digital form. For

		analog documents, we have a special room for that documents. I'm not sure if we publish this documents on our AIS.
Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		closed access, some with an embargo on when they will become publicly available
Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Closure periods
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Communicability restrictions
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Confidentiality and IPR: access restrictions, personal information: access restrictions, ensuring processing grounds, special storage (limited access) and protocol.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		confidentiality and personal information: storage on premise, technical measures like encryption and restricted access, organisational measures: access only after permission is retained/for specified purposes or after a specified period of time has elapsed property rights: public access only to low resolution representations, full access only for specified purposes
Protection of personal information		controlled Restricted Access settings
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study		Dark archive
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Data are not to be read by the common folk unless exception granted. Data are in a stongbox
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Data as much as possible anonymized. Data archived in local Data integration centrer

Protection of personal information		deposition in the archives with restricted access
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		designing protocols for access within the TDR yet to be implemented
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		different levels of preservation; licensing proces for IPR; ethical/privat blocking options; blocking of collection by tenant policies
Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Each collection object can have different limits as regards to rights to publish or distribute it. Also, the material or the metadata can have personal information that is protected. Only our museum staff - or researchers with permissions - has access to the protected data. If personal information of private persons is involved, we often publish the material with only e.g. first names, even if we do have the permissions to publish them in full.
Protection of intellectual property rights		Embargo, Restricted Access
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		Encryption, restricted access
Protection of personal information		Federal and Provincial Law
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		file/folder/information is locked
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Follow the five safes framework (approved researchers can access data in secure settings for the use in approved projects. All out outputs are screened to ensure they are non-disclosive).
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of		For all - note on the description of the record; user role limitations.

intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		For data that contains personal information we require that it includes documentation that the dataset can be archived and shared with indirect/direct person-identifying information. We also require a data processor agreement between the responsible institution and our archive that includes information about: The data that is to be archived. How long the data will be stored. The purpose of archiving the data, and Who can gain access to the data.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		For legally-protected PII, we label the collection/series 'restricted' in our content repository; if a researcher requests to see it, an archivist reviews the material first and creates copies to redact. For sacred indigenous knowledge, we currently do not allow access but are in talks with tribes to determine if other processes should be in place to allow access to appropriate tribal members.
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information		Highly Sensitive - Access can only be provided through an application to a panel of Judges (Need to Know basis) Sensitive - Access can be approved by Senior Management - Prosecutor, Registrar (Need to know basis)
Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		https://localcontexts.org/
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		[link].
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		if records contains sensitive data, we check that the person who wants to use it has the necessary permissions to do so.

Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		In the future, we will also keep national security files ("Protection of national security") if the technical requirements are met by then.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information		Ingest into digital preservation system and elimination of other digital copies. Data access is very limited,
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		legal holds [local authority name].
Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Limit the access and usage of the materials according to law, regulations and contracts.
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		Many specific security measures with the focus on organization and technology
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		metadata related to restrictions is kept in the item record and not made available for public request
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Other (please specify)	On conditions specified by legal agreements with business sector partners, but only if it is classified as confidential not data subjected to strict secrecy according to internal classification system	MFA, encryption at rest and in transit , verification of AL level of users.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Only applies to a very small number of collections but where appropriate, content is redacted or suppressed from systems that were available

Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Organization only accepts such data with explicit informed consent and then according to the stipulations for personal information protection in it (typically, de-identification and, frequently, additional access controls).
Protection of personal information		Our archive is operated as a dark archive. Access is not permitted to third parties. Our staff is trained.
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Positive ethic board vote before study start as requirement for data storage.
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Privacy Notice Publications + Data Handling Policy application
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Privacy: Objects are only available after motivated request until 100 years after creation. IP rights: websites only available in the reading room.
Protection of personal information		Protected in accordance with GDPR and university guidelines
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Protection is covered by the Freedom of Information Act 2000
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		protection period, anonymization etc.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Protection periods or restricted access for users.
Protection of national security;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Public archival material that contains classified and other secret data is available after a period of 40 years

		<p>from its creation unless otherwise specified by another law.</p> <p>In issues related to the protection of data confidentiality, the protection of personal data, and the right to access information concerning public documentary and public archival materials, as well as private archival materials, which are not regulated by Archival Law, the laws and other regulations governing the protection of data confidentiality, the protection of personal data, and the right to access information shall apply.</p> <p>Personal data in public archival material is available for use 100 years from the date of birth of the person to whom the personal data relates, or after the death of the person to whom the personal data relates. If the date of birth and date of death of the person are unknown, or if determining them is associated with disproportionate difficulties and costs, personal data in public archival material is available for use 70 years from the creation of that material.</p>
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Records are closed to members of the public under state archival legislation. Systems are built to enforce the restrictions
Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Research agreement, review prior to granting access, reduction of content
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Researchers use virtual machines to collect, process and analyze the data. The sensitive data that is not anonymised is not deposited in the institutional repository
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Restricted access

Protection of personal information		restricted access
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Restricted access to data
Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights		restricted access, under the control of the researcher/owner of the data record
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		Restricted or closed access
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		Restriction on access in repositories and AIPs stored in separate special locked-down storage.
Protection of national security;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		retention periods; access only within the archives; information instead of submission; closure of certain parts of the content; no online presentation of data and/or metadata; restricted online presentation of metadata
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		sec-levels of the DIMAG system according to state archives of [region].
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		Secure storage, Access control, restricted access,
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Sensitive data is made available through a data enclave / secure data

		center with onsite access and output control
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information		Since most of the studies archived with [xxx] contain information about individuals and therefore comprise private and/or sensitive information, pseudonymisation processes before the publication are inevitable. Pseudonymisation protect research subjects against identification, fulfil the requirements of data protection, and meet ethical research standards.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information		technical and organizational protection measures
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		The information is not accessed by the archivists directly and is maintained within the secure server zone of the [organisation], where stringent security protocols are applied to prevent access or loss of data. Sensitive information is also kept in a specified protection period, before the end of which it is not publically accessible.
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Other (please specify)	animal rights	The taken protection measure for each type of chosen sensitivity is limitation to the access to the data, e.g., restricted access, private links for sharing, custom license, information about ethical papers.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		unknown
Protection of human rights;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		We don't upload online, control access, and if necessary censor locations and photographs of human remains and funerary objects.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of		We have a special database which is run by a contractor. He is responsible

intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		for the safety measures taken but we set the framework.
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		We have access rules and automatic logs on the repository, including sole viewing
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		we have essentially a dark archive with limited and controlled access.
Protection of human rights;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		we hold them as closed files but have a process by which researchers can request access and potentially view them
Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information		We observe the legal protection periods.
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge		we use copyrights licenses and access rights according to collection needed protection. for national security we consult the appropriate state offices
Protection of personal information		We use protection periods.
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		We use Statute on archives and archival materials
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret		We use Statute on archives and archival materials

indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		
Protection of human rights;Protection of national security;Protection of confidentiality, the right to privacy, respect for human subjects of study;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of intellectual property rights;Protection of personal information;Protection of sacred and secret indigenous knowledge;Protection of rare, threatened or endangered species		We use Statute on archives and archival materials.
Protection of human rights;Protection of legal process and public order;Protection of personal information		We will not allow access to the documents stored in the repository, as they are judicial cases; only the involved departments and interested parties can access them until the 100-year confidentiality and personal data protection period has expired.

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Appendix C: Qualitative coding

NB: Textual data here is supplied verbatim, other than where identifying detail has been removed and replaced with 'xxx'. Codes assigned to all or part of each phrase are indicated in square brackets.

Q2.2 In your organisation, do you have an agreed or working definition of 'long-term' in the context of digital preservation?

Codes generated:

- 2.2 LTP designated community
- 2.2 Legal / admin obso(lescence)
- 2.2 ltp = 10 years +
- 2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP⁴²/unlimited period
- 2.2 ltp = min. 100 years
- 2.2 ltp tech change / obso(lescence)
- 2.2 ltp: 50 years +
- 2.2 ltp: as long as org(anisation) lifetime
- 2.2 ltp: until selected for deletion
- 2.2 ltp: usability important.

Data:

"A period of time long enough for there to be concern about the impacts of changing technologies, including support for new media and data formats." [2.2 ltp tech change / obso]In any case, the time horizon is >10 years. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

"for ever" [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

"for the foreseeable future" [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

"Long-term" is defined as retention for at least ten years in usable form. [2.2 ltp: usability important, 2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

(1) Forever: information transferred to National Archive is to be kept forever. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period](2) At least 100 years while information to preserve resides at Provider. [2.2 ltp = min. 100 years, 2.2 ltp: as long as org lifetime]

10 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

10 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

10 years and longer [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

10 years per organisation's commitment [2.2 ltp = 10 years +] plus best effort

10 years. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

⁴² = As Long As Possible.

10+ years for research data, 30+ for legally relevant measurement data [2.2 ltp = 10 years +] 100 years + [2.2 ltp = min. 100 years]

25+ years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

5 years and then migrate

50 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +, 2.2 ltp: 50 years +]

50+ years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +] [2.2 ltp: 50 years +]

A period long enough for technological change to occur (e.g., new versions of file formats, new known risks, new expectations of designated community, new software/OS versions, etc.). [2.2 LTP designated community, 2.2 ltp tech change / obso]

According to the requirements of Polish agency, the National Science Center, we define "long-term" as the statement that datasets and metadata should be stored for a period of time not shorter than ten years. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

All operations aimed at ensuring the preservation and access to documents for very long periods: several years, decades, or even indefinitely. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Any length of time that might be impacted by changing technologies and the changing of "Designated Community". [2.2 LTP designated community, 2.2 ltp tech change / obso]

Anything over a few years, while in continued use [2.2 ltp: usability important] - up to permanent preservation
Anything past the standard 10 or 25 year retention period. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Archives Law Section 1. Terms Used in this Law 19) record of permanent retention - a record which shall be stored forever in accordance with the Law; 22) temporary record - a record for which a short-term (up to 10 years) or long-term (more than 10 years) storage period has been determined; As an archive we define "long-term" as permanent as in "forever and ever" [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]but I notice that for IT people, researchers and other colleagues, "long term" is often seen as more than, say, 30 years. In that view, there is no organization-wide definition.

As an archive, we want to preserve digital documents for eternity and make them available to users. Therefore, we are developing strategies to ensure that data remains readable and understandable even 100 years from now. An archive without its users is merely a desolate repository for information that is never accessed. [2.2 ltp: usability important]

as long as possible (forever) [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

As long as possible, i.e., not restricted to a certain timespan [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] As the digital data publication journal, our organization promised to keep the online data long term preservation and public available At least 10 years. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Based of the organization's records retention schedule, long-term means those digital objects with permanent value, 50 years and above [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]. There are other digital contents which are temporary but still consider long-term because they are working records for as long as the organization remains in existence. [2.2 ltp: as long as org lifetime]

Currently only permanent records, that must be kept indefinitely, are preserved long-term. According to Article 16 of Resolution No. 324/2020 of the National Council of Justice of Brazil, permanent records are those with historical, evidential, or informational value that must be permanently preserved in their original format. The link: <<https://atos.cnj.jus.br/atos/detalhar/3376>> Data is converted into long-term preservation formats and guaranteed to be available for at least 50 years. [2.2 ltp: 50 years +, 2.2 ltp = 10 years +] For data that falls under curation level 1 or 2 and 10 years for level 3 data. The curation levels are decided based on the related documentation that we also receive from deponents and how it supplements the data itself.

decades or centuries [2.2 ltp = min. 100 years, 2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Define by retention schedules

Defined within the law on archival materials and archives, article 3., e) Digital Long term is 50 years or more with format check on a regular basis [2.2 ltp = 10 years +, 2.2 ltp: 50 years +] digital preservation as a strategy to preserve documents/information, "more than 100 years" [2.2 ltp = min. 100 years]

Documentary material in digital form for permanent storage is material whose content is recorded in digital form and stored on a machine-readable storage medium, whereby such digital form and storage medium ensure effective permanent storage and compliance with technological development.

For ever, unless removal requested or required. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

For more than 10 years after initial deposit. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

For research data at least 10 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

For the eternity [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

For the foreseeable future [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

For us "long-term" mean as long as possible. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] In accordance with French law on archives, we are responsible for providing and maintaining public access to all public data that can be disclosed. [2.2 ltp: usability important]

forever [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

forever [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

forever [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

the permanent preservation of archival materials in a manner that guarantees their availability and accessibility [2.2 ltp: usability important], including migration of the materials.

<https://dingo.psnc.pl/en/darceo-en/>

In perpetuity [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

In perpetuity, or at least for the next 50 years. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period, 2.2 ltp: 50 years +]

In the context of a pharmaceutical company "long-term" refers to the retention of data and records in compliance with regulatory and business requirements, typically spanning 5 to 40 years, and in some cases extending indefinitely. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +, 2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] Such indefinite

preservation necessitates the implementation of robust preservation planning strategies to ensure the integrity of archived materials over time.

indefinite [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Information that needs to be kept for longer than the system that currently holds it. [2.2 ltp tech change / obso]

Keep documents more than 100 years readable, [2.2 ltp = min. 100 years, 2.2 ltp: usability important] usable and retrievable legal requirements (Bundesarchivgesetz), unlimited preservation "until the end of all days" (in terms of demands) [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period, 2.2 ltp: usability important] Long term preservation of scientific data, allocation of unique identifiers for data, ensuring compliance with FAIR principles, with data long-term preservation planning and financial support.

long-term means unlimited and permanent [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Long-term preservation ensures that digital information remains accessible and usable. xxx does not specify a maximum storage period, i.e. that the data will be archived "forever". [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] Digital preservation is implemented on three levels: bit-level preservation, logical preservation, and semantic preservation.

Long-term preservation for us means that our research outputs are deposited in the institutional repository for at least 10 years. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Long-term refers to the ability to ensure the accessibility, usability, authenticity and integrity of digital materials over an indefinite period, potentially exceeding several decades and technological generations. [2.2 ltp: usability important, 2.2 ltp tech change / obso, 2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Longer than 10 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Longer than the period of administrative or legal value [2.2 Legal / admin obso]

Maintaining digital information so it remains accessible and usable over an unlimited period despite changes in technology or formats. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period, 2.2 ltp tech change / obso]

minimum 10 years to hold the data [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

minumum of 25 years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

No limit. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]Public status depending on a given embargo schedule.

Observations made of the environment (including atmospheric composition, weather and climate) cannot be reproduced - so if they are identified as important they must be curated & sustainably stored "forever". We set a minimum limit of 100 years for observations and ca 25-50 years for model outputs. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period, 2.2 ltp = 10 years +, 2.2 ltp = min. 100 years]

Our idea of "long-term" is explained here: xxx

Our policy requires the research data to be preserved for at least 10 years after the end of the project, if allowed by legal or contractual obligations. This period extends to 25 years for clinical trial data. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

Over ten years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

permanent preservation or long-term preservation [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

permanent retention. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Permanently, because State Archives are obligated to keep records (analog or digital) permanently preservation with no end date [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

Scheduled for transfer to the archives

ten years [2.2 ltp = 10 years +]

The aim of the xxx federal archives is to preserve the records of the xxx government in perpetuity. As such our definition of long-term is "in perpetuity" [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

The lifetime of our institution [2.2 ltp: as long as org lifetime]

the management of the archives is according to the definition of long-term The preserved item includes descriptive metadata about the work or recording, the digital content itself (bits), and administrative metadata. The data is stored in such a way that there are at least three separate copies located in distinct storage locations.

The purpose is to preserve the authenticity of digital copies of materials and the possibility of using copies as equivalent to the original material.

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The working definition is that we do not set a limit on the duration. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

To Permanently secure [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] (in legal terms digital records are treated the same as analogue records: (§2 HArchivG 13th. October 2022) über die Lebensdauer von Hardware und Software hinaus

Until "thinning" the archive mandates the digital objects are disposed of. [2.2 ltp: until selected for deletion]

Virtually indefinitely. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period] Mostly reevaluated every 10 years for reappraisal. [2.2 ltp = 10 years +, 2.2 ltp: until selected for deletion]

We are striving to keep objects usable and accessible "forever" [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period, 2.2 ltp: usability important] - practically this means we will take preservation actions as long as our organization exists [2.2 ltp: as long as org lifetime] and will hand over data to a successor or return it to the owners/depositors. No data will be deaccessioned unless for legal or ethical reasons.

We define "long-term" as forever. [2.2 ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period]

We don't have a definition, but long-term preservation is at the heart of the repository's mission. We permanently hold research data from studies that are substantive and methodologically sound, e.g. longitudinal data and internationally comparable data.

We follow the DPC's definition of long-term as meaning 'as long as necessary'.

We have an organisational mandate to preserve collections in perpetuity, so our definition of long-term is forever. [2.2 *ltp = forever/ALAP/unlimited period*].

Q3.5A: 'something else': Please specify what happens to data after the initial "long-term" preservation period.

Codes generated:

- 3.5 consult with depositor
- 3.5 continue to preserve
- 3.5 currently designing process
- 3.5 re-evaluate value of retention
- 3.5 reject notion "initial period"
- 3.5 transfer elsewhere

Data:

put them into the oasis conform long term storage system DIMAG. [3.5 continue to preserve]

Search out appropriate GLAMS to take possession of the digital and physical media. [3.5 transfer elsewhere]

We follow the recommendations of our referential organism (destruction, full long-term conservation or partial selection of data). [3.5 consult with depositor]

We continue to preserve it indefinitely. [3.5 continue to preserve]

long-term-preservation in the archival sense [3.5 continue to preserve].

Library asks archive to appraise the data. [3.5 transfer elsewhere]

10 for national funders, 15 for EU projects. We try to ask for an estimation of wanted preservation when data is deposited in the system chat interface. Logg for conversation saved in the data repository system and can be revisited after ten years in theory (service have not existed for that long). [3.5 consult with depositor]

we ask if they want some more yrs. [3.5 consult with depositor]

Depending on instructions from depositors: if they only intended 10y retention, we try to inform them about the expiry or have university archives assess relevance for permanent retention. Frequency of user requests for access during the first period will also be considered. If depositor selected permanent retention at deposit, this will usually be respected. [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention, 3.5 consult with depositor]

Our research data deposits are currently less than ten years old. We are in the process of establishing an agreement for deletion from preservation storage. [3.5 currently designing process]

It is usually extended. [3.5 continue to preserve]

continue the long-term preservation. [3.5 continue to preserve]

We keep curating it. [3.5 continue to preserve]

Re-evaluate for continued life-span. [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention]

In our case consulting of depositor is not feasible, usually they no longer exist. Depending on usage, we evaluate if we should continue to preserve or deposit the data with the National Archive of xxx (contractual agreement). [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention]

Data are assessed in terms of their potential long-term value. [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention]

Our definition of "long-term" reaches way longer than only 100 years. We keep them. [3.5 continue to preserve]

Definitive preservation. [3.5 continue to preserve]

Keep on preserving and giving access. [3.5 continue to preserve]

There is no end to the "long-term" preservation period, because we only keep permanent records. [3.5 continue to preserve]

We preserve data indefinitely or until the responsible organization asks for it to be deleted or returned to them. There is no "initial period". [3.5 continue to preserve, 3.5 reject notion "initial period"]

We continue to preserve the data: we are a historical archive. [3.5 continue to preserve]

Nothing, because data should be stored permanent. [3.5 continue to preserve]

We preserve data that we own so preserve to infinity. Or until we change our preservation or collection policies. [3.5 continue to preserve] There are old data which has no clear ownership, so we deal with those individually at appropriate times. We don't delete anything light hearted – we'll try to locate the source or the data and discuss the issues as needed. [3.5 consult with depositor, 3.5 re-evaluate value of retention]

We appraise the archival value, the value for later research, both in the specific research domain and/or cultural-historical in general, and we keep the selected data permanently and delete the other data. [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention, 3.5 continue to preserve]

In accordance with legal requirements, we retain digital objects indefinitely. Technically, we regularly copy digital objects every 5-6 years. [3.5 continue to preserve]

For the archives, "long-term" means as long as possible, there is no restricted time period. [3.5 continue to preserve]

we continue to preserve the data. [3.5 continue to preserve]

A new preservation period starts. [3.5 continue to preserve]

We maintain our collections in perpetuity, outside of deaccessioned records. [3.5 continue to preserve]

We have not recognized permanent preservation of records to have defined separate "initial" and "later" stages in the archives from the preservation point of view. [3.5 reject notion "initial period"]

Just before the agreed period ends, we inform the user that data will be deleted within a short period (typically one month). The user has the possibility to contact us and discuss about next steps. If the user does not react, data are deleted. [3.5 consult with depositor]

We ask the National Archive if they want it or not, if not, we delete after consulting the depositor. [3.5 transfer elsewhere, 3.5 consult with depositor]

Transfer to a patrimonial archives service. [3.5 transfer elsewhere]

We appraise and select the data for long-term preservation. [3.5 re-evaluate value of retention]

our customers decide how long to retain their content for and what happens at the end of the retention period (e.g. deletion, further retention, transfer). [3.5 consult with depositor].

Q4.4 Does your designated community have needs that your organisation does currently not address?

Codes generated:

Annotation/comment functionality

Better user services needed

Deposit/ingest problems

Digitisation

Discipline specialism

Format problems

Hardware/infra needs

I don't like the question

Information system

Ingest process needs improvement

Interoperability

Lack of long-term provision

Lack of records management provision

Lack support live data

Large data volumes

Lobbying/advocacy/relationship building

Missing rules/directives/policy

Proprietary format

Provenance issues

Qualitative data

Resource limits: Funding

Resource limits: Staffing

Searchability

Sensitive data/ Data protection

Software preservation

Structured data

User needs: Online access provision

User needs: pre-registration

Data:

Currently, the Canadian repository landscape doesn't yet allow for deposits of sensitive data. Having this need addressed could be a milestone to support our researchers. [*Sensitive data/ Data protection*]

e. g. more and faster server storage on preparation-level before transfer to DIMAG [*Hardware/infra needs*]; more lobbying for archives on a lower state level [*lobbying/advocacy/relationship building*].

Repository storage for sensitive data. [*Sensitive data/ Data protection*]

While our organization CAN address the need for our user community to be educated about / plan for data sharing from the beginning of each research project, the massive outreach needed for that is beyond our capacity. The main unmet need is one of awareness to come to us. *[lobbying/advocacy/ relationship building]*

We mainly focus on quantitative surveys, but we see a need for storage and archiving of qualitative studies as well. We do accept qualitative data as well, but cannot accept everything since there is a greater demand for security and privacy related to such data. We have a process going to increase our expertise in qualitative data. *[Qualitative data]*

archiving any kind of data according to funders requirements (not enough infrastructures for every discipline). *[Discipline specialism]*

Still images that are considered 'digitised' (such as object photography) are made available through our collections online [link]; For all other digital content (including born-digital still images and digitised audiovisual), there is no mechanism to provide online access to the designated community, students, researchers, or the general public. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

The capacity, both in terms of infrastructure and human resources, to process, absorb and make available large volumes. *[Large data volumes, User needs: Online access provision]*

Needs in the areas of digital trace data relating to accepting for preservation, documentation and access. Researchers would like to share and preserve their data but the legal situation often doesn't allow for it. Many open questions on how best to describe this data with metadata and how to make it accessible, esp. in case of really big datasets (high volume in storage). *[Sensitive data/ Data protection, Large data volumes]*

Ability to comment on and annotate records *[Annotation/comment functionality]*.

Sensitive data *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*; Large data (>5GB per file). *[Large data volumes]*

Preservation of sensitive data. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

1) Support for data with privacy protection needs *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*. 2) (Better) support for larger data. *[Large data volumes]*

Long term storage of sensitive data *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*; Enhanced storage for warm data (currently only provided as a basic service) *[Hardware/infra needs]*; Assessment of data quality against FAIR guidance.

the would like to have a service for pre-registration. *[User needs: pre-registration]*

A dark archive for data that must or shall be remain closed; *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]* and a larger limit for maximum file size. *[Large data volumes]*

The digital repository implementation project has not yet been completed, and, as it is part of an initial exploratory research scope, it does not yet cover the institution's massive production of digital judicial cases. *[Hardware/infra needs, Large data volumes]*

We require better measures to deal with non-datadriven research cultures.

Sensitive data. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Storage of health related research. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Very high security level (ISO) for preserved datasets. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

We cannot afford to digitize 99% of the important collections we've become aware of. *[Digitisation, Resource limits: Funding]*

law expert on data protection *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*.

preservation of sensitive data. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Frontoffice for data center to deposit raw data. *[Better user services needed]*

More access for researchers, more born-digital material made available. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

We don't have a code repository. *[Software preservation]* Better services for longitudinal data *[Better user services needed]*. Ideally, ingest process could be faster. *[ingest process needs improvement]*

We are an open access repository - collections deposited for preservation must be made publicly available with minimum required metadata. Some organisations cannot deposit because of a lack of metadata or issues with copyright and licensing of the material. *[deposit/ingest problems]*

We do not have a place currently that allows to publish research data. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

The humanities and arts interpretation and perception processes need to be based on correct information over the visual art objects by long-term digital preservation basis.

missing implementation rules and agreed directives. *[Missing rules/directives/policy]*

We are evaluating these needs currently.

Preservation of sensitive data, or data that requires specific protection. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

More digitization. *[Digitisation]*

long-term archiving of databases. *[Lack of long-term provision]*

We are underresourced for the amount of education and advocacy required to reach compliance with the Public Records Act, and do not have full use of the digital repository software owned by the University. *[Hardware/infra needs, lobbying/advocacy/ relationship building, Resource limits: Funding]* We do not yet properly preserve our digital records. *[Lack of long-term provision]*

Storage for sensitive/protected data or other data that cannot be shared openly. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Sensitive data *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]* & large data storage. *[Large data volumes]*

Archive has no information system. *[information system]*

integration with some specific metadata repositories (national archives in xxx) *[Interoperability]*.

We cannot currently handle data above 5 Tb/designated community. Primarily due to lack of funding, not a technical problem. But research funding not allowed to be used for long-time storage, and no free money at

administration. we actually wouldn't have that much storage without a donation of disc -but skilled people that runs the systems are very few. *[Resource limits: Staffing, Resource limits: Funding, Large data volumes]*

sensitive data. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

We do not have appropriate platform for providing born-digital access. In particular, rendering of complex file formats, and controlled access for staff access. *[User needs: Online access provision, Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Currently access processes to born digital records are highly manual. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

Easy combination of publication and archival of Metadata in one technical system.

(more automated analysis/tools of the data) to get more digital access. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

Human resource. *[Resource limits: Staffing]*

Enhanced data access service esp. interactive web-based; improved machine-accessibility; *[User needs: Online access provision]* improved provenance documentation and traceability. *[Provenance issues]*

handling of extremely large datasets (multi TB) for direct download *[Large data volumes]*, variable information on the landing pages, variable search.

Issues with computational notebooks and long term preservation. *[Software preservation]*

Digital data objects are displayed only in Gallica (compressed copy made for dissemination; visual or audio rendering only) or in the Wayback machine (web archives). We are just at the beginning of disseminating files as a complete copy to researchers. *[User needs: Online access provision, Better user services needed]*

We currently do not have a robust digital records management program, which is a blind spot for our institutional data. *[Lack of records management provision]*

Funding *[Resource limits: Funding]*, people *[Resource limits: Staffing]*, assistance with data storage *[Hardware/infra needs]*.

Sorry but this question is not a good one. How could one ever claim to be able to support 100% of all community needs. Our user community is very diverse. *[I don't like the question]*

User access to digital objects. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

We do not have a good way to collect and store oral history recordings. *[Qualitative data]*

Deep curation for qualitative data (currently developing better systems for this). *[Qualitative data]*

The need of a national open science policy. *[Missing rules/directives/policy]*

research software preservation. *[Software preservation]*

Preservation of large amounts of data, although this is not an organization specific problem. *[Large data volumes]*

long-term preservation of structured data, often in proprietary formats, from laboratory instruments, clinical trials systems, medical devices etc. *[Structured data, Proprietary format]*

Ability for leaving employees to easily collect all the data they produced during their career (from a xxx Archival system). *[Provenance issues]*

Some issues for the specification of accepted formats remain unsatisfactory for some in the designated community. For example the archiving of geodata has been addressed but not yet definitively resolved. *[Format problems]*

Long term availability of deposited data (after 10 years of project end) with semantic preservation. *[Lack of long-term provision]*

Highly sensitive data from human subject research cannot be preserved *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*; there is no clear solution for managing access to data which were deposited with closed access (owner decides about access requests) after the depositor has left the organisation or retired. *[Provenance issues]* Large data volumes (TB range) cannot easily be handled. Larger data not at all. *[Large data volumes]*

We limit the size of data deposits. *[Large data volumes]*

Publishing sensitive data, data with thousands of files, and data in the size of terabytes. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

Secure sharing within the research communities *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*, catering for size *[Large data volumes]*, a good policy for deleting data *[Missing rules/directives/policy]*.

SAE (archival electronic system).

e.g. virtual access to protected content after permission is granted *[User needs: Online access provision, Sensitive data/ Data protection]*, solution for long term preservation of some formats e.g. archived web content, *[Format problems]* rarer formats found in deposits, *[Format problems]* findability of archived web content *[User needs: Online access provision]*, searchability of archival contents *[searchability]*.

Easier access to e.g. legal deposit. *[User needs: Online access provision]*

digital reading room *[User needs: Online access provision]*

Saving for particularly large individual files. *[Large data volumes]*

sensitive data storage. *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*

We do not have any support for regularly-updated (eg daily updated) datasets. *[lack support live data]*

solutions for large amounts of data *[Large data volumes]*, restricted access options *[User needs: Online access provision]*, legal advice.

file size restrictions; *[Large data volumes]* sensitive data *[Sensitive data/ Data protection]*.

Q4.5 In your opinion, which factors could reduce the findability, accessibility, interoperability, or reusability over time of digital data objects preserved by your organisation?

Codes generated:

- 4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with
- 4.5 access issues
- 4.5 access/use vs. IP
- 4.5 API problems
- 4.5 archive/repository insufficiently known
- 4.5 budget/finance issues
- 4.5 capacity/demand: meeting
- 4.5 changes in standards/practices
- 4.5 changing user needs
- 4.5 changing/missing semantic artefacts
- 4.5 CMS changes
- 4.5 critical service disruption
- 4.5 curation standards changing
- 4.5 curation: insufficient
- 4.5 data obsolescence
- 4.5 data provenance issues
- 4.5 data volume/file sizes
- 4.5 designated community worries
- 4.5 digitation problems
- 4.5 disaster risk
- 4.5 discipline specific data: challenges
- 4.5 emulation issues
- 4.5 FAIR/open data: low engagement or understanding
- 4.5 file formats-too many
- 4.5 formats changing/obsolescence
- 4.5 formats, proprietary
- 4.5 formats: difficult to preserve
- 4.5 formats: inappropriate
- 4.5 increasing data complexity
- 4.5 information system issues
- 4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation
- 4.5 IPR issues
- 4.5 lack infra availability
- 4.5 lack infra maintenance
- 4.5 linking, insufficient
- 4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit
- 4.5 machine interoperability, lack of
- 4.5 management/org, lack of support from
- 4.5 metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies
- 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff(icient) quality
- 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing
- 4.5 need more guidance/ policy
- 4.5 not use of rec(ommended) formats
- 4.5 organisational changes/instability
- 4.5 political/legislative threats
- 4.5 poor data quality
- 4.5 preservation planning, errors in
- 4.5 proprietary hardware/equipment
- 4.5 search/ searchability: issues
- 4.5 security issues
- 4.5 sensitive data challenges
- 4.5 software issues

4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers
4.5 staffing, skill of
4.5 standardisation, need more
4.5 standards: inappropriate
4.5 technology change/obsolescence
4.5 training, need more
4.5 user needs: meeting
4.5 workflow, errors/problems in

Data:

a plethora of different file formats, *[4.5 file formats-too many]* bad quality of data *[4.5 poor data quality]*.

Access is through downloading whole files, which may be prohibitive for large file sizes. *[4.5 data volume/file sizes, 4.5 access issues]*

access to software used to create data sets so we can migrate/normalize the files for current and future access. *[4.5 access issues, 4.5 software issues]*

An increased web presence, and perhaps a digital research portal that allows the public to more easily access our collections and see what we have available. *[4.5 search/ searchability: issues]*

At the moment, the usage of the recommended file formats is very stable. A change in the data format could reduce the reusability. *[4.5 not use of rec formats, 4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]*

Bad maintenance of the physical et numerical structure housing the digital data objects. *[4.5 lack infra maintenance]*

ballancing IP protection and open to all. *[4.5 access/use vs. IP]*

Banned words lists, *[4.5 political/legislative threats]* too many hits *[4.5 capacity/demand: meeting]*, not good enough metadata from the start *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]*, not considering how to improve on existing metadata *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality]*.

Being unable to update published data to meet the needs of people who change how they find and use data, such as updating how data's described and file formats. *[4.5 changing user needs]*

budget cuts *[4.5 budget/finance issues]*.

budgetary restrictions *[4.5 budget/finance issues]*, not enough staff, *[4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]* proprietary software *[4.5 software issues]* and restrictive APIs *[4.5 API problems]*, general lack of knowledge about the importance of digital long term preservation *[4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit]*.

Catalog and data access *[4.5 access issues]*.

Change of political system *[4.5 political/legislative threats]* or legal system *[4.5 political/legislative threats]*. Technical issues *[4.5 lack infra maintenance, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence]* or insufficient e-accessibility *[4.5 access issues]*. Obsolescence of digital data. *[4.5 data obsolescence]*

Changing file formats *[4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]*; insufficient metadata to understand the data; *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]* changing ontologies *[4.5 changing/missing semantic artefacts]*; changing needs of the designated community *[4.5 changing user needs, 4.5 designated community worries]*.

Changing standards of data curation *[4.5 curation standards changing]*.

Changing technology causing data to become difficult to use *[4.5 technology change/obsolescence]*.

Complexity of data i.e. data chains, webcontent [4.5 increasing data complexity]. Complexity of software to render data. [4.5 software issues]

compression of subject-specific information in the fields "keywords" and "subject classification" [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]; absence of terminology standards covering our subjects palette; [4.5 changing/missing semantic artefacts] coarse and conflicting mandatory resource type classifications. [4.5 standards: inappropriate]

Content management system upgrade [4.5 CMS changes].

Migration to up to date formats to avoid data obsolesce. [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]

Enhanced and enriched metadata contents. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality]

continued use of inadequate staff to do this work. [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Current open source software has significant issues for searching and finding content. [4.5 search/ searchability: issues, 4.5 software issues]

Currently recovering from a cyber-attack. [4.5 security issues]

Disasters [4.5 disaster risk].

Disruption of services like DataCite; [4.5 critical service disruption] change in funder policies towards more restrictive international access; [4.5 access issues] use of even more different and not well established "standards" for data description [4.5 standards: inappropriate, 4.5 standardisation, need more]; lack of funding for maintaining LTP, repositories, or even plain data storage for growing volumes; [4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with, 4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 lack infra maintenance, 4.5 data volume/file sizes] non-scaling of technical solutions for preservation and of respective workflows [4.5 capacity/demand: meeting]. General lack of acceptance of FAIR and open data as guiding principles [4.5 FAIR/open data: low engagement or understanding] and lack of interest and understanding in preservation issues [4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit].

EAASI failing [4.5 critical service disruption][4.5 Emulation issues].

Errors in metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality], poor OCR [4.5 digitation problems], digital data objects initially created/ingested in lossy formats. [4.5 formats: inappropriate]

F&R: Badly chosen metadata profiles (not enough metadata) [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing].

Factors affecting Reusability: 1. inadequate documentation of how data was created, structured, or intended to be used, especially in regards to the archiving of databases. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] 2. Lack of provenance information. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 data provenance issues]

Failed migrations [4.5 workflow, errors/problems in, 4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation]; unnoticed technology evolution [4.5 technology change/obsolescence]; cyber-attack [4.5 security issues]; lack of reappraisal [4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation]; too much data [4.5 data volume/file sizes].

Failure to be able to open, understand, trust and reuse data because of (a) technical obsolescence of domain specific data formats, and (b) not maintaining records of authenticity and provenance such as audit trails and details of source systems and processes that are needed to establish the origin, accuracy, completeness etc. of the data. [4.5 data provenance issues, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]

file format obsolescence [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence], development of new metadata standards / validation methods. [4.5 changes in standards/practices]

File formats in certain disciplines are already difficult to preserve in the short-term (e.g. CZI files) [4.5 formats: difficult to preserve]. It is difficult to find the problems in discipline specific files as they are software/hardware dependent. [4.5 software issues][4.5 discipline specific data: challenges]

File formats may become outdated [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence], and software or hardware to open them may no longer be available [4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 software issues]. Documentation related to preservation and data use may be incomplete. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] Changes in standards or practices can complicate data handling [4.5 curation standards changing].

first of all missing usage licences are a factor. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 access/use vs. IP]

For example foulds in mapping meta data during the mapping within the process of data migration. [4.5 workflow, errors/problems in]

format changes [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence], software provenance, software environment [4.5 software issues], security issues due to US policy [4.5 political/legislative threats, 4.5 security issues].

format migration, [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence, 4.5 workflow, errors/problems in] size of the data (big data) [4.5 data volume/file sizes].

Formatobsoleszenz [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence], Finanzen [4.5 budget/finance issues].

From our perspective, longterm accessibility of digital data objects is particularly at risk due to the wide variety of file formats we manage, many of which are proprietary. These formats often lack sufficient documentation, making lossless migration difficult and increasing the risk of compromising data authenticity and semantic integrity over time. [4.5 formats: difficult to preserve, 4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with, 4.5 formats, proprietary]

Funding [4.5 budget/finance issues] and staff. [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Funding to create a proper digital preservation infrastructure, including the operational funding to pay staff to develop a policy and potentially consult with 3rd party specialists or vendors. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

funding [4.5 budget/finance issues], instability in formats [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence].

Funding [4.5 budget/finance issues], storage [4.5 lack infra maintenance].

funding [4.5 budget/finance issues], technology [4.5 technology change/obsolescence], attacks [4.5 security issues, 4.5 disaster risk] etc..

Funding [4.5 budget/finance issues].

Government instability [4.5 political/legislative threats].

Having someone to actually do the work in a dedicated manner.[4.5 staffing, skill of, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Hostile state or federal laws [4.5 political/legislative threats], natural disasters [4.5 disaster risk], poor stewardship over an extended period of time. [4.5 staffing, skill of]

human and financial resources [4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers].

Human factors that do not maintain standards [4.5 staffing, skill of].

I think interoperability is very difficult in the here and now, never mind the future! We have been running for over 20 years and so the challenge can be the effort required to adopt newer standards and the fact that there won't be enough resource (or benefit) from retrospectively changing things to the new standard. [4.5 *curation standards changing*]

If the stored datasets are not checked for many years. [4.5 *insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation*]

if we don't get good descriptions in English, researcher/data manager does not fill in information using the controlled vocabularies [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: insuff quality*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*], if we don't get time to do data quality control and format conversions [4.5 *staffing, insufficient numbers*, 4.5 *insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation*], if depositor choose not to provide a open license for the dataset. [4.5 *FAIR/open data: low engagement or understanding*]

If we wont use international standards, like FAIR, standardized Metadata or CC-BY Standards we will lose the connection to the users. [4.5 *standardisation, need more* , 4.5 *FAIR/open data: low engagement or understanding*] User want to get access to the material over the internet, but if we dont list our archival materials on portals like "Archivportal D", "Findbuch.net" or "Museana", the xxx archive will be forget rapidly. Archives should work for the society and should provide alot of information, which users can convert to knowlegde. Archives should always see themselves as service providers that are ready to provide people with new knowledge. [4.5 *user needs: meeting*]

Inability to expose & share metadata with "information brokers" & portals, e.g. by not applying expected standards for metadata content or not facilitating data access by (semi-)autonomous processing agents. [4.5 *standardisation, need more*]

incomplete compliance of some data to project standards [4.5 *standardisation, need more*]; partly incomplete and/or inconsistent metadata [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: insuff quality*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*]; large number of data providers with different ways of working and large number of data types [4.5 *file formats-too many*, 4.5 *data volume/file sizes*, 4.5 *increasing data complexity*]; large number and large volume of data [4.5 *data volume/file sizes*]; time restrictions [4.5 *staffing, insufficient numbers*].

Incorrect designation of license or origin of data. [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies*]

Informatical tools. [4.5 *user needs: meeting*]

Insecure financing for the longterm. [4.5 *budget/finance issues*, 4.5 *Long-term preservation: issues with*]

Insufficient contextual and provenance information [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*, 4.5 *data provenance issues*] and missing machine readable metadata [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*] as well as the currentlay inapliccability of standards within the domain. [4.5 *standards: inappropriate*]

insufficient implementation of representation model and description of hybrid records [4.5 *curation: insufficient*]; loose connection between repository and finding aid/archival information system [4.5 *information system issues*].

Insufficient infrastructure [4.5 *lack infra maintenance*], errors in archival workflows/pipelines [4.5 *workflow, errors/problems in*], conceptual errors in preservation planing [4.5 *preservation planning, errors in*], failing hardware [4.5 *technology change/obsolescence*].

Interoperability: too many different Metadata standards used. [4.5 *standardisation, need more*]

Reusability: Missing or unclear Metadata [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: insuff quality*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*].

Irregular maintenance of data [4.5 *insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation*] and the associated obsolescence of data. [4.5 *data obsolescence*]

lack of awareness for IPR and sufficient self-contained documentation on the side of the depositors [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]; use of non-open licenses [4.5 access/use vs. IP].

Lack of capacity / resources for format risk assessments and implementing appropriate actions. [4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation, 4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Lack of coherent policies and processes related to our designated digital repository (ExLibris Rosetta), because we have only transitioned to using Rosetta within the last year. [4.5 changes in standards/practices, 4.5 need more guidance/ policy]

Lack of curation [4.5 curation: insufficient], poor metadata quality. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality]

Lack of descriptive metadata included with deposits [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], limitation on search functionality (and rendering) for different repositories [4.5 search/ searchability: issues].

Our open research data repository has accepted link to other sites as deposits in the passed. We cannot provide assurances to long term accessibility for anything that we do not have the "raw data" for. [4.5 access issues, 4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with]

Lack of detailed embedded metadata may be an issue in the future. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] Changing formats and technical specifications will require migration. [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence]

lack of documentation [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing].

lack of finances [4.5 budget/finance issues], political restrictions on data publication/accessibility (e.g., censorship) [4.5 political/legislative threats].

Lack of funding and resource [4.5 budget/finance issues], lack of training [4.5 training, need more], lack of support from senior management [4.5 management/org, lack of support from], volume of collections [4.5 data volume/file sizes], poor or inadequate metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies], lack of clarity about copyright holders when permission is needed for reuse [4.5 IPR issues, 4.5 data provenance issues]; failing systems [4.5 lack infra maintenance, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence], environmental collapse.... [4.5 disaster risk]

Lack of funding!!! [4.5 budget/finance issues]

Lack of funding. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

Lack of funding. [4.5 budget/finance issues] Laws and regulations that encourage restrictions - such as copyright term extension or emulation restrictions. [4.5 political/legislative threats, 4.5 access/use vs. IP] Natural disaster. [4.5 disaster risk] Lack of technology hardware/resources or electricity due to climate change or war. [4.5 disaster risk]

lack of humanistic education.

Lack of information system [4.5 information system issues], lack of human resources [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers].

Lack of institutional policy and monitoring measures [4.5 need more guidance/ policy].

Lack of institutional support for the TDR [4.5 management/org, lack of support from], Funded administrative and management of the TDR. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

lack of maintenance of relationships between physical objects and digital surrogates. [4.5 linking, insufficient]

lack of metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], degradescence (degradation and obsolescence of content) [4.5 data obsolescence].

Lack of ongoing preservation [4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with].

Lack of open source formats [4.5 formats, proprietary], lack of sufficient metadata and documentation [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing].

lack of proper documentation of data [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], proprietary formats [4.5 formats, proprietary].

lack of resources to maintain infrastructure or keep evolving [4.5 budget/finance issues]; lack of public interest to advocate for funding [4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit, 4.5 budget/finance issues].

Lack of resources. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

Lack of resourcing - mostly in the staff required, but also the systems to manage the volume of digital records produced by the university. [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers, 4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 data volume/file sizes]

Lacking solution for preservation for certain formats, specifically proprietary software. [4.5 formats: difficult to preserve, 4.5 formats, proprietary]

Lacks of means, budget cuts that prevent us to adapt our infrastructure, procedures and competences to technical and legal evolution, and to new users expectations [4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 staffing, skill of, 4.5 lack infra maintenance, 4.5 budget/finance issues]. The speed of technical evolution is a challenge [4.5 technology change/obsolescence]. AI could be a strong help but only if we get the financial means to use it. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

leadership and staff changes [4.5 organisational changes/instability], data loss, system migrations [4.5 information system issues].

legal uncertainty. [4.5 political/legislative threats]

level of description, [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] structure of data needing emulation [4.5 emulation issues], proprietary formats [4.5 formats, proprietary], obsolescence [4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 data obsolescence].

Limited indexing [4.5 search/ searchability: issues]. Media obsolescence. [4.5 data obsolescence, 4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]

Loss of corporate knowledge, failure of the software [4.5 software issues], poor metadata records [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality].

Loss of digital preservation system [4.5 information system issues], no longer supporting staff with digital preservation responsibilities. [4.5 management/org, lack of support from]

many experimental procedures require manual data conversion to open formats, and a large part of the data are analyzed vendor provided proprietary software tools. [4.5 formats, proprietary]

Migration to new archival software [4.5 workflow, errors/problems in, 4.5 software issues].

missing human resources for "caretaking" of the digital data. [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Missing metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], poor described readme-files [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality].

More restricted access due to privacy issues, technology changes and format obsolescence [4.5 access issues] [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence] [4.5 technology change/obsolescence], lack of representation information [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], trying to store everything in PDF instead of keeping closer to original formats [4.5 formats: inappropriate], proprietary formats [4.5 formats, proprietary], transferring information to us too late, a too hierarchical method of presentation of archives that makes it harder for (younger) people to find information. [4.5 changing user needs, 4.5 access issues]

More staff to manage digital data. [4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

no agreed or updated data management policy. [4.5 need more guidance/ policy]

no central concept for archiving at all. [4.5 need more guidance/ policy]

No factors reduce these factors, the longterm digital preservation is a active standard and necessity.

no regular migration of data. [4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation]

no specific requirements for formats [4.5 need more guidance/ policy, 4.5 file formats-too many], no quality check for metadata entered [4.5 workflow, errors/problems in, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality], no requirements to link datasets and published work. [4.5 linking, insufficient]

Non adherence to standardised vocabularies, [4.5 standardisation, need more] 'flat' metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality], increased number of collections held in the repository [4.5 data volume/file sizes], lack of awareness of repository in research communities [4.5 archive/repository insufficiently known], lack of promotion/awareness amongst staff in member organisations. [4.5 archive/repository insufficiently known]

none.

not all the data is searchable. [4.5 machine interoperability, lack of, 4.5 access issues, 4.5 search/ searchability: issues]

Not enough machine-interoperability. Maintaining especially interoperability and reusability requires human expertise on domain specific issues as well IT, sufficient resources and continuity of core activities and functions (instead of relying on project funding) [4.5 machine interoperability, lack of, 4.5 budget/finance issues]. Lack of citing data as independent research output and lack of incentives to cite. [4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit]

Not enough metadata, [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] closed / proprietary formats [4.5 formats: inappropriate, 4.5 formats, proprietary], very strict access conditions. [4.5 access issues]

Not have the infrastructure to deposit and make available sensitive data. [4.5 sensitive data challenges, 4.5 access issues] Lack of human resources or features that help us to check if the access to the data is still active. [4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]

Obsolence of the technology used (e.g. file formats interoperability). [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence] Semantic artefacts sustainability. [4.5 changing/missing semantic artefacts] Appropriate metadata richness. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]

Our data is mostly used internally to prepare artworks for display to the public in the galleries. Access by researchers is currently very limited. There are currently changes to our xxx team, which is responsible for out digital preservation infrastructure, that I feel put at risk the ability to maintain an up-to-date, safe infrastructure. [4.5 software issues, 4.5 organisational changes/instability, 4.5 security issues, 4.5 staffing, skill of]

Our data repository cannot support hierarchical data natively, folders need to be zipped, which makes content less searchable/indexable. [4.5 search/ searchability: issues]

Our organization does not provide stewardship, just preservation. Our members need to take the appropriate actions to implement these practices.

Participating people, losing know-how on fluctuations. [4.5 staffing, skill of, 4.5 organisational changes/instability]

People with no proper education [4.5 staffing, skill of], old technology [4.5 lack infra maintenance, 4.5 technology change/obsolescence]

People with no proper education, old technology.

Permanently archived materials are stored in a location with no access or very limited access [4.5 access issues]; there is no access to the digital content itself (only to the metadata); [4.5 access issues] the search system is poor; [4.5 search/ searchability: issues] the reliability or authenticity of the materials cannot be guaranteed. [4.5 data provenance issues, 4.5 poor data quality]

policy and funding sustainability [4.5 budget/finance issues] [4.5 organisational changes/instability];

Political oppression and defunding of all disability programs in the U.S [4.5 political/legislative threats].

Poor and unclear metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality].

poor metadata (technical, descriptive, rights) [4.5 IPR issues, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing], obsolescence [4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 data obsolescence].

poor metadata quality [4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality], proprietary formats [4.5 formats, proprietary], intellectual property rights. [4.5 IPR issues]

Poor/inaccurate metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing].

Preservation in our institution is not really possible. Having data in tapes enable large data storage but reduce the possibility to check for data integrity. We have no proper system able to check data stored in tapes. [4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation]

Primarily: lack of paradata and other contextual information. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]

Public service institutions often struggle with a lack of continuity in preservation policies, whether for physical or digital records, due to political changes in government. As a result, the entire structure—comprising technologies, personnel, processes, and regulations—can undergo changes, which directly impacts the longterm maintenance of records. [4.5 political/legislative threats, 4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with, 4.5 organisational changes/instability]

Reduction in funding. [4.5 budget/finance issues]

reduction in funding [4.5 budget/finance issues].

reduction in platform funding and staff attrition [4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers].

Relevant context material not published/deposited alongside research data, which therefore might not be preserved (method, provenance, process metadata, code, research software, standards etc.) [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]. Missing information about dependencies and environments in case of research

software. *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]* Changing technologies and standards, leading to deprecated and/or obsolete functions, obsolete versions of the technology or obsolescence of the full technology. *[4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 changes in standards/practices]*

Funding cuts / insufficient funding of access platforms and preservation activities. *[4.5 budget/finance issues]*

Researchers are free to store data with file formats that are not interoperable or machine readable. *[4.5 need more guidance/ policy, 4.5 machine interoperability, lack of, 4.5 formats: inappropriate]*

Researchers don't use good practices for their data sets - bad structuring of files, wrongly used metadata, etc. i.e. no RDM literacy. *[4.5 need more guidance/ policy, 4.5 not use of rec formats, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality, 4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit]*

resources *[4.5 budget/finance issues]*.

Restrictions by laws concerning copyright and handling of personal information. *[4.5 political/legislative threats, 4.5 IPR issues, 4.5 sensitive data challenges]* Also funding, of course... *[4.5 budget/finance issues]*

Reusability: Data in exotic formats for which no migration path exists. *[4.5 formats: difficult to preserve, 4.5 formats: inappropriate]*

Datasets may be deleted after reappraisal. Will still be findable as metadata will be kept, but no longer be accessible. *[4.5 Long-term preservation: issues with]*

security issues of all sorts *[4.5 security issues]*.

Several factors may reduce FAIRness over time, such as outdated metadata *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality]*, obsolete file formats, lack of rights information, insufficient documentation, and limited resources for quality assurance. *[4.5 insufficient appraisal/migration/checks/curation, 4.5 formats changing/obsolescence, 4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 IPR issues, 4.5 budget/finance issues]*

Software obsolescence *[4.5 software issues]*, proprietary software *[4.5 software issues]* and specialist/proprietary hardware *[4.5 proprietary hardware/equipment]*.

Some main factors are: 1) Insufficient content/information quality of the data *[4.5 poor data quality]*. 2) Insufficient quality of descriptive metadata *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: insuff quality]*. 3) Data stored in file formats that are not suitable for longterm preservation and cannot be migrated to more suitable format(s). *[4.5 formats: inappropriate]*

Staff resourcing to manage collections and implement system controls/mechanisms to provide access to complex born-digital materials. *[4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]*

Stall in the development of data-related schemas. *[4.5 changing/missing semantic artefacts]*

Sustainability of file formats *[4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]*; Access controls. *[4.5 access issues]*

technical development, less human or financial resources *[4.5 budget/finance issues, 4.5 staffing, insufficient numbers]*.

technical problems of storage *[4.5 lack infra availability]*, format problems *[4.5 formats: difficult to preserve]*.

Technological obsolescence, particularly of file formats *[4.5 technology change/obsolescence, 4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]*, and sometimes loss of representational information *[4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing]*.

technological obsolescence [4.5 *technology change/obsolescence*], use of proprietary standards [4.5 *formats, proprietary*], insufficient content information [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*], fragmented datasets. [4.5 *poor data quality*]

technological progress, which is a threat to the anonymity of the subjects in the data (may ultimately mean that some data has to be taken offline if we cannot guarantee that re-identification cannot happen) [4.5 *sensitive data challenges*]; to a lesser extent technological change and changes in the knowledge base of our designated community. [4.5 *technology change/obsolescence*, 4.5 *designated community worries*]

That the continuity of secure management, storage and accessibility of the data is interrupted. And in this way the trustworthiness is compromised and information is lost. [4.5 *security issues*]

the anything-goes-thinking.

The auto generated metadata are not always correct. And this corruption of data is hard to find and fix. [4.5 *metadata/ documentation: insuff quality*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies*]

The current lack of a digital preservation system and preservation storage, the lack of a delivery system for both digitised audiovisual and all born-digital formats, plus the current lack of investment and resource required to undertake digital collecting and digital preservation currently restricts or prevents the (FAIR) use of digital content in our collection. [4.5 *access issues*, 4.5 *budget/finance issues*, 4.5 *lack infra availability*]
Going forward, investment will be required if we are to be able to align with FAIR principles and both preserve and provide access to digital content in our collection. [4.5 *budget/finance issues*]The biggest challenge will be all the complex digital objects. [4.5 *increasing data complexity*, 4.5 *formats: difficult to preserve*]

the lack of metadata (researchers doesn't have the time or motivation to complete descriptions that are crucial for FAIRification). [4.5 *FAIR/open data: low engagement or understanding*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*]

The largest factor would be if we do not have the capacity to archive all the data, preserve it and make it available etc. Although our organisation is large, the archive is only a smaller part of it, so being understaffed is the largest factor. [4.5 *staffing, insufficient numbers*]

The loss of the catalog system could pose a temporary problem. By preserving basic, descriptive metadata, searches remain possible. If the archival information system no longer exists, we can resort to a flawed exit strategy. [4.5 *information system issues*]

The main factor is longterm financial sustainability. [4.5 *budget/finance issues*]

the main factor that could reduce these qualities in our digital data over time is having the available resources, both to create the metadata (staff/time resources) and to index the metadata in a searchable system (staff/financial resources). [4.5 *staffing, insufficient numbers*, 4.5 *budget/finance issues*, 4.5 *search/ searchability: issues*]

the object is deleted due to request by owner/lack of funding = operation ends/... [4.5 *budget/finance issues*]

the recommended list of file format did not been repeat over the time. The risk exist that some file will not be readable in the futur. [4.5 *formats: inappropriate*, 4.5 *formats changing/obsolescence*, 4.5 *formats: difficult to preserve*]

The reduction of personnel and financial ressources. [4.5 *budget/finance issues*, 4.5 *staffing, insufficient numbers*]

The use of a variety of file formats, the large nature of the datasets in the repository and the lack of documentation regarding the research methodology will impact the reusability over time. [4.5 *data volume/file sizes*, 4.5 *file formats-too many*, 4.5 *metadata/ documentation: missing*]Add to this is the fact that

a large number of researchers use their own scripts or develop their own software. We are only now trying to consider with software preservation looks like but this is far away from being implemented [4.5 software issues].

The will of the authors to implement our recommendations.

unknown data stewards and people who do not understand needs of archives. [4.5 low general awareness imp of dp/infolit, 4.5 staffing, skill of]

Use of not-preferred file format by researchers; [4.5 formats: inappropriate]

Preferred file formats may become obsolete; [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]

We accept a lot of risky file formats and don't document them well enough. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing, 4.5 formats: difficult to preserve]

We have lots of digital data with less than ideal amounts of meta data recorded. [4.5 metadata/ documentation: missing] I also imagine we by now have lots of data in formats that are no longer supported fully by current software, or won't be in the future any longer. [4.5 formats changing/obsolescence]

We recently acquired xxx as our digital repository and preservation system. As a government agency in xxx, right now our funding is precarious. That is probably our number one concern. We're lucky that we're state funded, but it's not outside the realm of possibility that we could lose funding in the next several years. We've done everything we can to prevent that, but it is still a much bigger fear than minor data loss from not following standards 100%. [4.5 political/legislative threats, 4.5 budget/finance issues]

Wrong or inadequate tools [4.5 workflow, errors/problems in], lack of funding [4.5 budget/finance issues], inaccurately typed metadata [4.5 metadata/ documentation: inaccuracies], scripting, no standardized fileformats, [4.5 formats: inappropriate, 4.5 standardisation, need more] lack of knowledge on how to use the data, lack of understanding frameworks and guidelines, lack of reaching out to researchers and other user groups [4.5 archive/repository insufficiently known].

Appendix D: Informed consent agreement

Informed Consent Statement

Project: EOSC EDEN, WP1, task 1.1 Survey

You are invited to participate in an online survey to contribute to understanding of standards and practices for identification, selection and appraisal of digital data objects for long-term preservation, as part of the EOSC EDEN project. Before your participation, please read the following information carefully to understand the purpose of the study and what your participation involves.

PROJECT STATEMENT

- As part of our project collaboration, we would like to inform you that the data collected and results generated during this study will be processed and shared between the two sister projects, EOSC EDEN (Grant Agreement nr 10118801) and FIDELIS (Grant Agreement nr 1011880).
- This study will be managed in line with the privacy notice shared between the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects (privacy policy [here](#)). All data gathered will be used for the project and study purposes. Anonymised data or results may also be utilised for future relevant Open Science initiatives.

STUDY STATEMENT

- The purpose of this study is to investigate **understanding of standards and practices for identification, selection and appraisal of digital data objects for long-term preservation.**
- Survey data will be gathered by the EU Survey platform (data privacy statement [here](#)).

PARTICIPATION:

- Your participation in this study is voluntary.
- If you choose to discontinue your participation, you may withdraw at any time without penalty or negative consequences.
- If you withdraw from this project after completing the study, the original files containing your data may be destroyed at your request where feasible. However, the study results circulated via online or offline means may remain available, making your consent practically irrevocable once given.

RISKS:

- No risks are foreseen from this study. Any information likely to be damaging to your reputation will not be reported. The text of any attributed quote will be made available to you for approval before its initial publication. You will not be asked any questions about sensitive or personal topics.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

- All data collected in this project will be stored securely and only be accessible to the project partners of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS during the project period. Your responses will be

anonymized before publishing, meaning that your name and any other identifying information will at no point be linked to your answers. If you have any concerns about this, please contact us at privacy.edenfidelis@postit.csc.fi before proceeding.

DISSEMINATION:

- By participating, you consent to the use of the anonymized data collected during this study along with the findings generated, which will be used for project purposes, including online and offline presentations and publications.
- By participating, you consent to the use of findings generated from the data that will be published on the joint website of the EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS projects when available and may also be posted to project social media channels (i.e., LinkedIn and BlueSky).
- By participating, you consent to the archiving of an anonymised version of your data in a data repository approved by the data controller.

CONTACT:

- If you have any questions or concerns about the project or privacy issues, or if you wish to file a complaint, please contact our project ethical group at privacy.edenfidelis@postit.csc.fi.
- For inquiries specifically related to the study content, you may reach out to the data collector at laura@codata.org.

I have read and understood the information in this document, and I have received an answer to all my questions regarding this research. I give my consent to have an anonymised version of my data archived in a data repository approved by the data controller.

Appendix E: Survey invitations in various languages

- English version

Suggested subject line:

Digital preservation colleagues: please share your expertise on identification, selection and appraisal with the EDEN project!

Text:

In [EOSC EDEN](https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025), we are interested in how digital preservation professionals across the globe currently work, and we need input from your organisation. We are keen to understand the existing frameworks, guidelines and practices for identification, selection and appraisal of data for “long-term” preservation – and what “long term” means in different organisational and professional settings. This is an important area where sharing knowledge can make a meaningful impact as digital preservation continues to grow as a diverse field and community.

To that end, we're running an inquiry to gather, compare and evaluate current knowledge and practice. We need your help to gain a more comprehensive picture of these frameworks, guidelines and practices in the field. Written from the perspective of digital preservationists working within the sector, we have created a **short and focused survey** which should take no more than about five to seven minutes to complete: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Please can you share this request with the person or people in your organisation responsible for digital preservation activity?

Whether you work in **research, cultural heritage, industry, or another sector**, and whether you are part of a large organisation or a small team, we would like to hear from you. The survey is suitable for members of staff at any level in the organisation and does not ask for any sensitive information. Multiple responses from the same organisation are welcome. We hope that, as colleagues across the digital preservation world, you will take a few minutes to share information with us about your current practices, and the guidelines and frameworks that inform your decisions.

The survey is open until 30 June 2025. Please take part now at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

For any questions about the survey or the work of EDEN WP1, please contact WP Lead, Micky Lindlar at [Micky.Lindlar\[at\]tib.eu](mailto:Micky.Lindlar[at]tib.eu) or Task Lead Laura Molloy at [laura\[at\]codata.org](mailto:laura[at]codata.org).

Thank you for sharing your expertise – your contribution is incredibly valuable!

- French version

Suggested subject line:

Professionnel·le·s de la préservation numérique, partagez votre expertise sur l'identification, la sélection et l'acquisition avec le projet EDEN !

Text:

Au sein du projet [EOSC EDEN](https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025), nous nous intéressons aux méthodes de travail actuelles des professionnel·le·s de la préservation numérique à travers le monde, et nous avons besoin de retours de votre organisation. Nous souhaitons comprendre les cadres de référence, consignes et pratiques actuelles d'identification, sélection et acquisition de données en vue de leur préservation « à long terme » – et le sens que ce « long terme » a dans différents contextes organisationnels et professionnels. C'est un domaine important où le partage de connaissance peut produire un effet concret alors que la préservation numérique continue à se développer, à la fois comme champ d'étude et comme communauté.

Dans ce but, nous menons des recherches pour réunir, comparer et évaluer le savoir et les pratiques actuelles. Nous avons besoin de votre aide pour obtenir une vision plus complète de ces cadres de référence, consignes et pratiques du domaine. A partir de l'expérience de spécialistes de préservation numérique, nous avons créé **une enquête brève et orientée** qui devrait vous prendre cinq à sept minutes à remplir : <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Pourriez-vous partager cette demande avec la ou les personne(s) responsable(s) de la préservation numérique dans votre organisation ?

Que vous travailliez **dans la recherche, le patrimoine culturel, l'industrie ou tout autre secteur**, que vous fassiez partie d'une grande organisation ou d'une petite équipe, nous souhaiterions avoir votre avis. L'enquête est adaptée à des personnels à tout niveau d'une organisation et ne demande pas d'information sensible. Nous encourageons les réponses multiples issues d'une même organisation. Nous espérons qu'en tant que collègues travaillant dans la préservation numérique, vous prendrez quelques minutes pour partager avec nous vos pratiques actuelles et les consignes et cadres de référence qui guident vos décisions.

L'enquête est ouverte jusqu'au 30 juin 2025. Participez maintenant sur : <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Pour toute question sur l'enquête ou les activités du *work package* WP1 du projet EDEN, merci de contacter Micky Lindlar, responsable du WP1 (micky.Lindlar[at]tib.eu) ou Laura Molloy, responsable de tâche (laura[at]codata.org).

Merci de partager votre expertise – votre contribution est vraiment précieuse !

- German version 1: more personal

Liebe Kolleginnen und Kollegen,

gerne möchte ich Sie auf eine **Umfrage zum Thema „Identifizierung, Auswahl und Bewertung in der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung“** aufmerksam machen, die derzeit im Rahmen des **EU-Horizon Projekt [EOSC EDEN](#)** durchgeführt wird. Sie richtet sich an alle Personen, die in der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung tätig sind, und wir würden uns freuen, wenn Sie sich als Fachkolleg:innen ein paar Minuten Zeit nehmen könnten, um uns Informationen über Ihre derzeitigen Abläufe und die Leitlinien und Standards, die Ihre Entscheidungen beeinflussen, mitzuteilen.

Untenstehend finden Sie den Link zur Umfrage und weiterführende Informationen. Vielen Dank für Ihre Teilnahme!

Mit freundlichen Grüßen

NAME

Im EU-Horizon Projekt [EOSC EDEN](#) untersuchen wir, wie Fachkräfte im Bereich der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung auf der ganzen Welt arbeiten. Solch ein Austausch von Wissen ist von großer Bedeutung, zumal die digitale Langzeitarchivierung als heterogenes Feld und diverse Fach-Community kontinuierlich wächst. **Dafür benötigen wir Ihre Unterstützung.**

Wir sind sehr daran interessiert, Ihre etablierten Konzepte, Leitfäden und Praktiken für die Identifizierung, Auswahl und Bewertung von Daten für die „langfristige“ Archivierung zu verstehen - und was „langfristig“ in verschiedensten organisatorischen und fachlichen Umgebungen bedeuten kann. **Aus diesem Grund führen wir eine kurze Umfrage durch, um den aktuellen Wissens- und Praxisstand zu erfassen.** Die Umfrage wurde von Spezialist:innen aus dem Bereich digitale Langzeitarchivierung ausgearbeitet und nimmt nicht mehr als fünf bis sieben Minuten Ihrer Zeit in Anspruch: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Ob Sie in der Forschung, im Kulturbereich, der Industrie oder in einem anderen Bereich tätig sind, ob Sie Teil einer großen Organisation oder eines kleinen Teams sind - wir freuen uns, von Ihnen zu hören! Die Umfrage ist für Mitarbeiter:innen aller Organisationsstufen geeignet und es werden keine sensiblen Informationen abgefragt. Mehrere Antworten aus derselben Organisation sind willkommen. Bitte teilen Sie diese Anfrage daher auch mit Personen in Ihrer Organisation, die für digitale Langzeitarchivierung verantwortlich sind.

Die Umfrage ist noch bis zum 30. Juni 2025 geöffnet. Bitte nehmen Sie jetzt teil unter:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Für Fragen zur Umfrage oder zur Arbeit von EDEN Work Package 1 stehen Ihnen gerne Work Package Lead Micky Lindlar unter Micky.Lindlar[at]tib.eu oder Task Lead Laura Molloy unter laura[at]codata.org zur Verfügung.

Vielen Dank für das Teilen Ihres Erfahrungsschatzes – Sie leisten damit einen globalen Beitrag zur digitalen Langzeitarchivierung!

- German version 2: less personal

Suggested subject line:

Feedback aus der LZA-Praxis gesucht: Eosc EDEN Umfrage zu Identifizierung, Auswahl und Bewertung in der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung

Text:

Im EU-Horizon Projekt [EOSC EDEN](#) untersuchen wir, wie Fachkräfte im Bereich der digitalen Langzeitarchivierung auf der ganzen Welt arbeiten. Solch ein Austausch von Wissen ist von großer Bedeutung, zumal die digitale Langzeitarchivierung als heterogenes Feld und diverse Fach-Community kontinuierlich wächst. **Dafür benötigen wir Ihre Unterstützung.**

Wir sind sehr daran interessiert, Ihre etablierten Konzepte, Leitfäden und Praktiken für die Identifizierung, Auswahl und Bewertung von Daten für die „langfristige“ Archivierung zu verstehen - und was „langfristig“ in verschiedensten organisatorischen und fachlichen Umgebungen bedeuten kann. **Aus diesem Grund führen wir eine kurze Umfrage durch, um den aktuellen Wissens- und Praxisstand zu erfassen.** Die Umfrage wurde von Spezialist:innen aus dem Bereich digitale Langzeitarchivierung ausgearbeitet und nimmt nicht mehr als fünf bis sieben Minuten Ihrer Zeit in Anspruch: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Wir würden uns freuen, wenn Sie sich als Fachkolleg:innen ein paar Minuten Zeit nehmen könnten, um uns Informationen über Ihre derzeitigen Abläufe und die Leitlinien und Standards, die Ihre Entscheidungen beeinflussen, mitzuteilen

Ob Sie in der Forschung, im Kulturbereich, der Industrie oder in einem anderen Bereich tätig sind, ob Sie Teil einer großen Organisation oder eines kleinen Teams sind - wir freuen uns, von Ihnen zu hören! Die Umfrage ist für Mitarbeiter:innen aller Organisationsstufen geeignet und es werden keine sensiblen Informationen abgefragt. Mehrere Antworten aus derselben Organisation sind willkommen. Bitte teilen Sie diese Anfrage daher auch mit Personen in Ihrer Organisation, die für digitale Langzeitarchivierung verantwortlich sind.

Die Umfrage ist noch bis zum 30. Juni 2025 geöffnet. Bitte nehmen Sie jetzt teil unter: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

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Vielen Dank für das Teilen Ihres Erfahrungsschatzes – Sie leisten damit einen globalen Beitrag zur digitalen Langzeitarchivierung!

- Spanish version

Asunto sugerido:

Colegas de la conservación digital: por favor, ¡compartan su experiencia en identificación, selección y evaluación con el proyecto EDEN!

Texto:

En [EOSC EDEN](#), estamos interesados en conocer cómo trabajan actualmente los profesionales de la preservación digital en todo el mundo, y para ello necesitamos información sobre su organización. Estamos interesados en comprender los marcos de trabajo, directrices y prácticas existentes para la identificación, selección y valoración de datos susceptibles de ser conservados a "largo plazo" - y lo que significa "a largo plazo" en diferentes entornos organizativos y profesionales. Esta es un área de trabajo importante donde el intercambio de conocimientos puede tener un impacto significativo a medida que el diverso campo y comunidad de la preservación digital continúa creciendo.

Con este fin, estamos realizando una encuesta para recoger, comparar y evaluar los conocimientos y las prácticas actuales. Es por ello que necesitamos su ayuda para obtener una imagen más completa de estos marcos, directrices y prácticas. Hemos elaborado una breve encuesta en inglés, escrita desde la perspectiva de las personas

encargadas de conservar los archivos digitales. Completarlo no le llevará más de cinco a siete minutos:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Estaríamos agradecidos si pudiera compartirlo con la persona o personas de su organización responsables de llevar a cabo la preservación digital.

Nos gustaría conocer su opinión tanto si trabaja en el ámbito de la investigación, del patrimonio cultural, de la industria o de otro sector, como si forma parte de una gran organización o de un pequeño equipo. La encuesta puede completarse por personal de cualquier nivel y no solicita ningún tipo de información sensible. Asimismo, múltiples respuestas de la misma organización son bienvenidas.

Esperamos que, como colegas del mundo de la preservación digital, puedan dedicar unos minutos a compartir con nosotros información sobre sus prácticas actuales y las directrices y marcos que guían sus decisiones.

La encuesta permanecerá abierta hasta el 30 de junio de 2025. Es posible participar desde ahora mismo en :

<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Para cualquier pregunta sobre la encuesta o el trabajo del equipo EDEN WP1, por favor póngase en contacto con WP Lead, Micky Lindlar en Micky.Lindlar@tib.eu o Task Lead Laura Molloy en laura@codata.org.

Gracias por compartir su experiencia - ¡su contribución es increíblemente valiosa!

- Chinese Version

标题：欧盟EOSC EDEN项目邀请您参与问卷调查：分享您在数据识别、遴选与评估方面的专业知识！

您好！

我们是来自EOSC EDEN 项目的研究员。[EOSC EDEN](#)是一个由欧盟支持的多国合作研究项目，我们致力于了解全球数字（科技文献）资源保存的现行工作方式。这个项目主要关注如何对需要长期保存的数据进行识别、遴选与评估，以及其现有的框架、指南及实践，和在不同机构与专业语境中的具体含义。

我们正在开展一项问卷调查，旨在全球收集、比较和评估这个领域当前的知识体系与实践经验。我们诚挚地邀请您或者您单位的学者/员工参与此问卷调查，这将帮助我们更全面地把握该领域的框架、指南及实际操作。我们设计了一份简洁的专题问卷（约需5-7分钟完成），该问卷从数字保存工作者的视角出发。

本问卷适用于各级别学者/员工，且不涉及敏感信息收集。烦请您将本问卷转达给贵机构负责数字资源保存工作的相关人员。无论您来自科研机构、文化遗产领域、企业还是其他行业，无论您身处大型组织还是小型团队，我们都期待您的反馈。同一机构的多份反馈尤为欢迎。作为数字保存领域的同行，我们真诚希望您能抽出几分钟时间，分享当前的实践方式及决策所依据的指南框架。

此问卷为英文，将开放至2025年6月30日。点击链接即可参与：<https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

如您有任何疑问，可用英文联系负责人Micky Lindlar研究员（Micky.Lindlar@tib.eu）和Laura Molloy研究员（laura@codata.org），或者用中文联系张芬博士（fen.zhang@kuleuven.be）。

感谢您愿意分享您在数字科技文献资源的长期保存上的专业知识！

祝好,

EOSC EDEN 项目研究组

- Dutch version

Oproep tot deelname aan de EOSC EDEN survey - Help ons begrijpen hoe digitale preservatie professionals werken!

Het [EOSC EDEN project](#) werkt rond de langetermijnbewaring van FAIR (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable*) data en is geïnteresseerd in hoe professionals op het gebied van digitale archivering en langetermijnbewaring momenteel werken. Specifiek zoeken we naar input van de digitale archiveringsgemeenschap in het gebruik van bestaande praktijken, standaarden, richtlijnen en werkwijzen voor de identificatie, selectie en beoordeling van data voor langetermijnbewaring – en wat 'lange termijn' betekent in verschillende organisatorische en professionele contexten. Dit is een belangrijk gebied waar kennisdeling een betekenisvolle impact kan hebben, zeker nu digitale preservatie blijft groeien als een divers vakgebied.

Daarom voeren we een onderzoek uit om de huidige kennis en werkwijzen te verzamelen, vergelijken en evalueren. We hebben uw hulp nodig om een zo volledig mogelijk beeld te krijgen van deze kaders, richtlijnen en werkwijzen in het vakgebied. Digitale preservatie deskundigen werkzaam binnen de sector hebben we een korte en gerichte enquête opgesteld die niet meer dan vijf tot zeven minuten in beslag neemt: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Of u nu werkt in onderzoek, cultureel erfgoed, de industrie of een andere sector, en of u deel uitmaakt van een grote organisatie of een klein team, we horen graag van u. De enquête is geschikt voor medewerkers op elk niveau binnen de organisatie en vraagt niet om gevoelige informatie. Meerdere antwoorden van dezelfde organisatie zijn welkom. We hopen dat u, als collega's in de digitale preservatiewereld, een paar minuten de tijd neemt om informatie met ons te delen over uw huidige werkwijze en de richtlijnen en kaders die uw beslissingen beïnvloeden.

De enquête loopt tot 30 juni 2025. Doe nu mee via: <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/EOSC-EDEN-T1survey2025>

Voor vragen over de enquête of het werk van EDEN WP1 kunt u contact opnemen met WP-leider Micky Lindlar via Micky.Lindlar@tib.eu of met Laura Molloy via laura@codata.org.

Bedankt voor het delen van uw expertise – uw bijdrage is ongelooflijk waardevol!